

INTRODUCTION

Navigating data gaps and data needs for marine biodiversity policy implementation

As Europe accelerates its efforts to address biodiversity loss and climate change, policy makers and environmental managers face a significant hurdle: the critical lack of high-resolution, standardized data on the status and extent of marine habitats. Implementing ambitious frameworks like the Nature Restoration Regulation and the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), among others, requires more than just observations; it demands actionable information that can bridge the gap between complex science and effective policy implementation.

The OBAMA-NEXT contribution

The Horizon Europe OBAMA-NEXT project (Observing and Mapping Marine Ecosystems – Next Generation Tools) is specifically designed to meet this demand. The project’s core goal is to develop and demonstrate innovative, cost-effective technologies for mapping and monitoring marine biodiversity across Europe’s diverse sea basins. By leveraging the latest advancements in remote sensing, autonomous platforms, optical sensors, and molecular tools, OBAMA-NEXT provides the evidence base needed to achieve Good Environmental Status (GES) and support nature-based climate solutions.

The path to information products

At the heart of the project are its Information Products. These are not just datasets or technologies; they are refined tools designed to answer specific management questions. The process of developing an Information Product can vary with its nature and problem being addressed. Nevertheless, the Information Products developed and fine-tuned in OBAMA-NEXT follow an integrative approach, combining:

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Diverse Data Sources: Integrating traditional *in situ* field observations – data collected through scientific diving and video surveys – with high-tech sensors mounted on drones, gliders, buoys, FerryBoxes, etc.
-
Advanced Analytics: Utilizing artificial intelligence, machine learning, and statistical modeling to translate raw data into comprehensive maps of habitat distribution, ecosystem condition and ecosystem services, such as blue carbon.
-
Policy-Driven Design: Every product was developed with the specific data needs and reporting requirements of EU biodiversity policies and Regional Sea Conventions (OSPAR, HELCOM, Barcelona, and Bucharest) in mind.

What you will find inside

This booklet serves as a comprehensive “White Book” of the OBAMA-NEXT Information Products. It is a project deliverable, intended to serve as a catalogue for policy makers and stakeholders. Inside, you will find a collection of factsheets, each detailing a specific tool, how it works, and exactly which policy indicators it supports.

From quantifying blue carbon sequestration to environmental DNA and habitat mapping through machine learning, these Information Products are designed to address recognized data gaps and data needs for policy implementation. By providing repeatable and reproducible monitoring solutions, this compendium offers the foundation necessary to move from policy planning to measurable environmental action across European seas. For more detailed information on each Information Product and the technical details on how to implement them, please read other OBAMA-NEXT deliverables, such as D4.3 Catalogue of tools/products generated, and D1.2 Guidelines for practitioners, which are available in the project website.

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PLANKTON

ENVIRONMENTAL DNA RUN-OFF BIOINDICATORS

Summary

This Information Product develops a European approach for using eDNA-based microbial indicators to detect and rank river run-off influence on coastal and offshore waters. By analysing microbial community signals through metabarcoding, the product identifies bioindicator taxa associated with freshwater inputs from land, supporting early warning of coastal ecosystem change even where hydrological signals may be transient. The work focuses on standardising indicator identification across European regions and provides transferable outputs that can strengthen monitoring strategies in sensitive aquatic environments.

Description of the Information Product

The Information Product applies eDNA metabarcoding to microbial communities to identify across European seawater basins common taxa that act as bioindicators of river run-off and land-derived influence in marine waters. It addresses the need for a coherent European framework for bioindicator use, seeking common taxa and suggested thresholds that can support comparable monitoring and management approaches across Member States and sea basins. The concept is grounded in the observation that river run-off can drive measurable ecological consequences in coastal systems, including changes linked to nutrient enrichment, turbidity and reduced light availability.

The work consolidates and compares datasets across three OBAMA-NEXT learning sites spanning Atlantic and Mediterranean conditions and three different water basins (Bay of Biscay, Thau Lagoon, and Tyrrhenian Sea). The product produces operational outputs including the relative abundance of indicator taxa and a ranked characterisation of run-off impacted waters across coastal and offshore gradients.

Location of the Learning Sites where the Information Product was developed and tested.

How it works

- Water samples are collected across estuarine and coastal gradients with standardized and comparable methods;
- Environmental DNA is extracted and analysed using microbial metabarcoding;
- Common taxa associated with freshwater and land-derived inputs are identified as bioindicators across samples and European water basins;
- Relative abundance patterns are used to rank levels of run-off influence;
- Outputs are standardised across sites to enable cross-regional comparability.

IN SITU OBSERVATION OF PHYTOPLANKTON BLOOMS

Summary

This Information Product enhances the detection and monitoring of (harmful) phytoplankton blooms through high-frequency, *in situ* observations. By integrating automated sensors and high-throughput imaging across multiple platforms, it provides a “step forward” in understanding bloom phenology. This approach addresses the temporal gaps of traditional ship-based sampling, offering a repeatable framework to track bloom timing, duration, and intensity across European sea basins.

Description of the Information Product

Phytoplankton blooms are critical indicators of ecosystem health, yet traditional monitoring often misses their onset and peak due to infrequent sampling. This product addresses this limitation by deploying a multi-platform strategy that combines FerryBox systems, fixed autonomous stations, and satellite observations. This integrated approach allows for the continuous monitoring of biomass accumulation and species composition in near real-time.

The product provides high-resolution data on the occurrence and strength of blooms, specifically focusing on descriptors like timing, peak intensity, and duration. By utilizing automated imaging and optical sensors, it allows distinguishing between different phytoplankton groups, including cyanobacteria. This data is essential for identifying ecological shifts, assessing eutrophication levels, and providing early warnings for harmful algal blooms (HABs) that impact both ecosystem functioning and human activities.

Location of the Learning Site where the Information Product was developed.

How it works

- Uses high-frequency fluorescence sensors;
- Employs FerryBox and fixed platform systems;
- Integrates satellite and *in situ* observations;
- Automates species identification via imaging;
- Provides near real-time data workflows;
- Detects bloom timing, duration, and intensity;
- Standardizes data across different monitoring platforms.

Relevance for EU Biodiversity Policies

Bucharest Convention

The product could contribute to the monitoring of phytoplankton biomass and abundance, supporting seasonal trend analysis for the Black Sea by providing essential data on the abundance of blooming species and community composition. By tracking parameters such as the diatoms-to-dinoflagellates ratio and the biomass of specific taxa, the product could help Member States fulfil regional requirements for assessing the state of pelagic biodiversity.

Marine Strategy Framework Directive

The product directly supports monitoring for multiple Descriptors, most notably Eutrophication (D5). It provides primary data for D5C2 (Chlorophyll-a levels) and D5C3 (number, duration, and extent of HAB events). Furthermore, the product can contribute to monitor under D1C6.

OSPAR

The product supports data needs for biodiversity and eutrophication descriptors by providing high-frequency data on phytoplankton biomass and community shifts. It addresses data needs regarding nutrient-related impacts, such as changes in photic conditions and oxygen levels. Its automated workflows ensure methodological coherence across the North-East Atlantic, facilitating the assessment of plankton species composition and abundance trends.

Water Framework Directive

The product strengthens ecological status assessments in transitional and coastal waters by providing high-resolution biological signals. It supports the monitoring of phytoplankton composition, abundance, and biomass, which are key biological quality elements. The high-frequency nature of the data allows for a more accurate interpretation of ecological status, particularly in areas prone to rapid environmental changes or nutrient enrichment.

Example of taxon-specific and total filamentous cyanobacteria biomass obtained using this information product. Source: Kraft et al (2025).

To know more about this Information Product, read the publication by [Kraft et al \(2025\) Harmful Algae. Monitoring cyanobacteria blooms with complementary measurements—a similar story told using high-throughput imaging, optical sensors, light microscopy, and satellite-based methods.](#)

PHYTOPLANKTON TYPES AT THE DEEP CHLOROPHYLL-A MAXIMUM (DCM)

Summary

This Information Product maps the Deep Chlorophyll Maximum (DCM) — the ocean layer with the highest phytoplankton biomass — and characterizes its dominant phytoplankton types. By combining multi-platform *in situ* data with ecosystem modelling, the product overcomes the limitations of satellite observations, which cannot resolve subsurface communities. It provides a comprehensive assessment of phytoplankton biomass and diversity, essential for understanding marine food webs and ecosystem functioning.

Description of the Information Product

In marine environments, the DCM represents a critical, highly productive layer that is persistent in low-latitude regions and emerges seasonally in higher latitudes. Monitoring this layer is vital as it underpins key biogeochemical processes like carbon export and nutrient cycling. While satellite methods effectively estimate surface Chlorophyll-*a*, they are unable to capture the dynamics of the subsurface communities residing in the DCM.

This product addresses this gap by integrating a wide array of *in situ* observations, including data from buoys, gliders, Argos and research vessel cruises, with laboratory analyses like flow cytometry and microscopy. When data resolution is insufficient, the product utilizes hydrodynamic-biogeochemical models to infer spatial extent and predict DCM dynamics at broader scales. Tested in the Mediterranean Sea (Aegean and Tyrrhenian Seas), this multi-method approach allows for the determination of spatiotemporal variability in DCM depth, magnitude, and the specific pico-phytoplankton groups that dominate this productive layer.

Location of the Aegean and Tyrrhenian Seas Learning Sites.

How it works

- Collect water samples during regular research vessel cruises, from the entire euphotic zone, to characterize phytoplankton biomass and at least one method for characterizing phytoplankton diversity (flow cytometry, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography, microscopy, imaging, or other approaches);
- Measure Chlorophyll-*a* concentration using *in situ* fluorescence sensors with platforms covering the entire euphotic zone (e.g. buoys, gliders, Bio-Argo floats);
- Maintain high-frequency observations at multiple depths of the euphotic zone (e.g. from fixed platforms);
- Integrate data into hydrodynamic-biogeochemical models for upscaling;
- Apply ecosystem modeling to detect DCM depth and magnitude;
- Validate model predictions using all available *in situ* data, including satellite and Ferrybox surface data.

Relevance for EU Biodiversity Policies

Bucharest Convention

If modified for the Black Sea environment, this product can provide data on phytoplankton biomass and abundance, which address needs regarding the status of community composition, including seasonal trends and the biomass of blooming species. Its ability to resolve vertical distribution can support regional indicators, such as the diatoms/dinoflagellates ratio when applied to this region.

HELCOM

The product can support biodiversity assessments by providing information on phytoplankton species composition, abundance, and biomass. If modified for the Baltic Sea environment, it can have the capacity to address related data gaps in pelagic habitat status and community structure. This contributes to a more harmonized understanding of primary production and plankton lifeform abundances across regional monitoring programs

Marine Strategy Framework Directive

The product is directly relevant to Descriptor 1 (Biodiversity) and Descriptor 5 (Eutrophication).

It supports indicator D1C6 by assessing pelagic community structure and species composition within the water column. Additionally, it contributes to D5C3 by providing data on the number, duration, and extent of harmful algal bloom events, addressing key impact indicators for marine environmental status.

OSPAR

The product can identify changes in phytoplankton community composition, biomass, and abundance. If modified for OSPAR regions, it can contribute to biodiversity indices and help evaluate the direct and indirect effects of eutrophication.

Water Framework Directive

The product can provide data on composition, abundance, and biomass of phytoplankton in coastal and transitional waters. By providing detailed vertical resolution of phytoplankton types, it enhances the capacity of Member States to evaluate the ecological status of water bodies. The methodology supports the identification of biomass shifts that may indicate pressures on water quality and ecosystem health.

Aerial image of a phytoplankton bloom.

TROPHIC EFFICIENCY IN MARINE PLANKTON FOOD-WEBS

Summary

This Information Product focuses on evaluating marine ecosystem health and functioning by monitoring two critical metrics: phytoplankton resource-use efficiency and plankton energy/food web efficiency. By integrating in situ biomass data with nutrient concentrations and size-spectra analysis, the product quantifies how effectively phytoplankton exploit limiting nutrients and how efficiently energy is transferred across all plankton trophic levels. This approach provides a size-based framework that complements traditional taxonomic methods to better understand the structural efficiency of marine food webs.

Description of the Information Product

The Information Product provides a comprehensive perspective on ecosystem dynamics by linking microbial processes to broader plankton ecosystem functioning. It is divided into two parts: assessing the capacity of phytoplankton to exploit limiting nutrients (RUE) and quantifying the efficiency of energy transfer through the planktonic food web (FWE). While traditional taxonomic or molecular approaches can identify what species are present, they cannot directly quantify the efficiency of energy flow.

The product utilizes: i) RUE to quantify the phytoplankton capacity to transfer limiting nutrients from the environment into the planktonic food web and ii) FWE using Normalized Biomass Size Spectra, a unique method that collapses diverse taxa into a single size-based framework reflecting predator-prey interactions and total system stability. Tested in the oligotrophic South Aegean Sea (Cretan Sea), this product uses a time series constructed with plankton samples from regular research vessel cruises (in combination with fixed platforms for auxiliary environmental data). The product offers a standardized way to compare the efficiency of ecosystems across different trophic statuses, providing critical insights into how ecosystem health is maintained under varying environmental pressures.

Location of the Cretan Sea Learning Site.

How it works

- Collect water samples using Niskin bottles during repeated cruises at the same station;
- Measure phytoplankton biomass (e.g. Chlorophyll-*a*) and diverse limiting nutrient concentrations. Calculate the ratio of phytoplankton biomass to the concentration of the most limiting nutrient;
- Analyze plankton cells abundance using flow cytometry and/or microscopy techniques;
- Capture zooplankton via vertical tows with mesh nets during repeated cruises in the same station;
- Perform high-resolution image analysis on scanned zooplankton samples;
- Convert abundances to carbon units using literature relationships;
- Organize biomass data into Normalized Biomass Size Spectra and calculate trophic efficiency.

Relevance for EU Biodiversity Policies

Barcelona Convention

The product is relevant for monitoring eutrophication (Ecological Objective 5). It addresses the need for data on the concentration of key nutrients and Chlorophyll-a in the water column. By mapping resource-use efficiency, the product provides a more nuanced understanding of how nutrient inputs affect primary productivity in the Mediterranean

Bucharest Convention

If modified for the Black Sea environment, this product can contribute with data on eutrophication and nutrient concentrations as well as mesozooplankton biomass. It can provide partial data for reporting on Chlorophyll-a concentrations and the maximum concentrations of inorganic nitrogen, phosphorus, and silicate in the surface layer. This supports the assessment of pressure indicators related to nutrient loading and ecosystem response

HELCOM

If modified for the Baltic Sea environment, this product can be utilized in providing phytoplankton biodiversity data and for zooplankton and phytoplankton abundance and biomass.

Marine Strategy Framework Directive

The product is relevant to MSFD Descriptor 1 (Biodiversity), Descriptor 4 (Food Webs), and Descriptor 5 (Eutrophication). It supports indicator D1C6 by providing data on plankton. Additionally, it contributes to D4 indicators by quantifying energy transfer through the food web and supports D5C1, D5C2 by monitoring nutrient and chlorophyll levels.

OSPAR

The product can support monitoring of nutrient concentrations in seawater, marine food webs and eutrophication. If modified, it can contribute to indicators assessing the production of phytoplankton and changes in the average trophic level of marine predators. The NBSS methodology can specifically address data needs for plankton lifeform abundances shifts resulting from direct or indirect eutrophication effects.

Water Framework Directive

The product provides detailed data on nutrients and the composition, abundance, and biomass of phytoplankton. While focused on pelagic systems, its regular monitoring of biomass and nutrient use can help Member States evaluate the ecological status of coastal and transitional waters. The product's ability to detect system disturbances through size-spectra analysis enhances the capacity to diagnose environmental pressures.

Example of calculation of Resource Use Efficiency obtained using this information product.

SPATIAL DISTRIBUTION OF PHYTOPLANKTON BIOMASS BASED ON CHLOROPHYLL-A

Summary

The Information Product provides validated satellite-derived chlorophyll-a (Chl-a) concentration maps across European marine regions as a proxy for phytoplankton biomass. The product evaluates existing Copernicus Marine Service chlorophyll products and, where standard algorithms are unsuitable, implements the custom OSPAR-CCI processor. This mature operational product supports eutrophication monitoring, water quality assessment, and marine ecosystem management by delivering continuous spatial coverage of phytoplankton biomass at 300m to 1km resolution across diverse European waters from the Arctic to the Mediterranean.

Description of the Information Product

The Information Product provides maps of the spatial distribution of phytoplankton biomass based on satellite-derived Chl-a concentration for European seas. It evaluates and, where necessary, improves existing Copernicus Marine Service (CMS) Chl-a products by comparing them against an extensive multi-site *in situ* dataset collected at OBAMA-NEXT Learning Sites across the North-East Atlantic, Arctic, Baltic, Mediterranean and Black Seas.

For each Learning Site, the product selects the most suitable Chl-a algorithm by quantitatively assessing satellite-*in situ* matchups using statistical metrics such as correlation coefficient, slope, RMSE and median absolute percentage difference. Where standard CMS Chl-a products are found to be sufficiently accurate (e.g. in the Norwegian Sea, Fram Strait, Black Sea), the existing CMS products are adopted directly.

Location of the Learning Sites involved in the development of this Information Product.

How it works

- Collect satellite-based ocean colour observations;
- Remove the effects of the atmosphere (gases, aerosols, clouds) from the satellite signal;
- Algorithm Selection and chlorophyll retrieval;
- Validation with *in situ* measurements;
- Generate spatial maps and time series.

In optically complex, turbid shelf waters such as the Eastern English Channel and adjacent North Sea and Celtic Sea, the product replaces the standard products by a dedicated processor that generates the regional OSPAR-CCI Chl-a product, derived from the OC-CCI/GlobColour processing chain and using an algorithm-switching scheme based on OC5 and GONS-type approaches with quality-control tests.

The product provides basin- to regional-scale maps of surface chlorophyll-a concentration at high temporal frequency, suitable for monitoring phytoplankton biomass dynamics, bloom conditions and long-term trends. These maps support eutrophication assessment and ecosystem state indicators under MSFD, WFD, OSPAR and HELCOM by delivering spatially consistent, validated Chl-a information that complements traditional ship-based monitoring.

Relevance for EU Biodiversity Policies

Bucharest Convention

The product can be used to support biodiversity monitoring specifically in the case of phytoplankton mass and abundance.

HELCOM

The product provides relevant data specifically for eutrophication monitoring, such as Chl-a concentration and summer bloom intensity.

Marine Strategy Framework Directive

The product can contribute to data needs for Descriptor 5 (Eutrophication) if modified, as Chl-a concentration is a core indicator for assessing eutrophication status and achieving Good Environmental Status.

OSPAR Convention

The product supports better monitoring specifically in relation to population demographics and changes in community composition, notably changes in phytoplankton abundance. If appropriately applied, the product supports monitoring under the 'Eutrophication' descriptor. Satellite Chl-a products provide spatial coverage for OSPAR Regions II (Greater North Sea) and III (Celtic Seas).

Water Framework Directive

The product contributes with data for ecological quality assessment, in particular, Chl-a thresholds define ecological status boundaries (high/good/moderate/poor/bad) for coastal and transitional waters.

Example of the map obtained when applying the information product. The left panel shows algorithm selection and the right panel shows the resulting merged map. Source: Lavigne et al. (2021).

To know more about this Information Product, you can consult the forthcoming data paper on multi-site chlorophyll-a validation and algorithm selection for European seas. Additional methodological details on the OSPAR-CCI / RBINS multi-algorithm processor and its quality-control tests for OC4, OC5 and NIR-red (GONS-type) chlorophyll algorithms are provided in [Lavigne et al. \(2021\) Remote Sensing of Environment. Quality-Control Tests for OC4, OC5 and NIR-red Satellite Chlorophyll-a Algorithms Applied to Coastal Waters.](#)

DETECTION OF HARMFUL ALGAE BLOOMS FROM REMOTE SENSING

Summary

This Information Product enables the detection and monitoring of harmful algal blooms (HABs) using hyperspectral remote sensing technology. By leveraging spectral algorithms and NASA's PACE Ocean Colour Instrument, it provides early warning capabilities for toxic algal events in European marine waters. The product specifically targets detection of *Phaeocystis globosa* blooms in the North Sea and cyanobacteria in the Baltic Sea, supporting coastal management, water quality assessment, and public health protection through timely identification of potentially harmful phytoplankton accumulations.

Description of the Information Product

The product applies hyperspectral remote sensing methods to distinguish harmful algal bloom species from benign phytoplankton communities. Within the OBAMA-NEXT project, this product has demonstrated successful detection of *Phaeocystis globosa* blooms in the North Sea using the Modified Astoreca Line Height (MALH) algorithm applied to NASA PACE Ocean Colour Instrument (OCI) data and in-situ hyperspectral measurements from PANTHYR and HYPSTAR radiometers. The methodology exploits the fine spectral resolution (5 nm) of hyperspectral sensors to identify unique pigment absorption signatures characteristic of harmful species.

Unlike multispectral sensors (Sentinel-3 OLCI) which lack sufficient spectral detail to distinguish between phytoplankton groups in optically complex coastal waters, hyperspectral data from PACE enables detection of subtle spectral features in the 470–490 nm range that are diagnostic for specific harmful algae species. The MALH algorithm calculates a line height based on three wavelengths (470 nm, 482.5 nm, 490 nm) to detect the characteristic absorption signature of *Phaeocystis globosa*.

Location of the Learning Sites where the product was tested.

The product has been validated with *in situ* observations and chlorophyll-a data, demonstrating spatial correspondence between MALH index values and known bloom locations.

How it works

- Collect hyperspectral marine ocean colour data (satellite or *in situ*);
- Remove Atmospheric Effects from the satellite data;
- Analyse Unique Colour "Fingerprints" to identify harmful algae species;
- Create Detection Maps;
- Validation with water samples and microscope observations;
- Provide early warning information to coastal authorities and public health officials.

Relevance for EU Biodiversity Policies

EU Bathing Water Directive

The product supports compliance monitoring under the Bathing Water Directive by providing early warning of potentially toxic cyanobacterial blooms in coastal bathing areas. Timely detection enables authorities to issue public health advisories, protecting swimmers and beachgoers from exposure to harmful algal toxins. The spatial coverage of satellite monitoring complements traditional sampling at designated bathing sites.

HELCOM

Under HELCOM's efforts to combat eutrophication, the product informs the assessment of cyanobacterial bloom intensity and spatial extent in the Baltic Sea.

Marine Strategy Framework Directive

The product directly supports assessments of Descriptor 5 (Eutrophication) by providing spatial information on harmful algal bloom extent and frequency. HAB detection aids Member States in monitoring eutrophication-related pressures and assessing the effectiveness of nutrient reduction measures. The product contributes to understanding pelagic habitat quality and phytoplankton community composition changes that indicate ecosystem health status.

OSPAR Convention

For the North-East Atlantic, the product facilitates monitoring of *Phaeocystis globosa* blooms, which are a recognized eutrophication-related phenomenon in OSPAR waters. The product provides quantitative spatial data on HAB occurrence to support OSPAR's Common Indicators and assessment of eutrophication status. Early detection capabilities enable improved management of shellfish aquaculture activities and protection of coastal recreational uses.

Water Framework Directive

The product provides information for assessing ecological status of coastal and transitional waters under this directive. HAB occurrence is a key indicator of water quality deterioration related to nutrient enrichment. The spatial coverage and temporal frequency of satellite-based HAB detection complements traditional monitoring programs, enabling more comprehensive assessment of phytoplankton communities and their response to management interventions.

Chlorophyll a concentration map obtained using this Information Product in the Belgian coastal waters for three days during the 2025 spring bloom. Source: Lavigne et al. (2025).

To know more about this product, read the proceeding paper published by [Lavigne et al. \(2025\)](#) in the [WHISPER 2025 conference proceedings on successful detection of *Phaeocystis globosa* blooms from PACE hyperspectral data](#). Additional information is available from [Lavigne et al. \(2021\)](#) on inter-band calibration for hyperspectral water remote sensing (IGARSS 2021), which describes the methodological foundation for accurate spectral analysis required for HAB detection algorithms.

REGIONAL HARMONIZATION OF PHYTOPLANKTON IMAGE LABELS

Summary

This Information Product focuses on the harmonization and standardization of phytoplankton image labeling using emerging imaging technologies. By developing consensus among experts on taxonomic identification from digital images, it ensures consistent data reporting across different monitoring programs.

Description of the Information Product

The product addresses the critical need for standardized guidelines in phytoplankton monitoring, in particular the need for a regional coordinated effort to minimize the variability of automated classification systems. It establishes a collaborative framework where taxonomic experts reconcile discrepancies in image-based identification, particularly for challenging groups such as flagellates and dinoflagellates. By creating a bridge between traditional methods and new imaging devices, the product provides a reliable foundation for automated classifiers and harmonized datasets across the region. This exercise facilitates the integration of high-resolution imaging data into official monitoring networks, improving the frequency and spatial coverage of biodiversity observations. Although the product was developed for the Baltic Sea region, it can provide a model to be followed in other EU regions where the available technologies are improving consistency in the reporting of phytoplankton biodiversity.

Location of the Learning Site where the Information Product was tested.

How it works

-
 Conducts harmonization exercises with regional phytoplankton experts
-
 Utilizes imaging devices to capture high-resolution morphotype data
-
 Identifies taxonomic resolution limits based on specific morphotypes
-
 Aggregates images to improve label agreement among experts
-
 Develops standardized guidelines for metadata and data reporting
-
 Creates a consensus-based list for automated image classification.

Relevance for EU Biodiversity Policies

Bucharest Convention

The product can provide reliable data on phytoplankton community composition, which is a key element for assessing biodiversity state. It addresses data needs regarding phytoplankton biomass and abundance, as well as the identification of blooming species and diatoms/dinoflagellates ratios.

HELCOM

The product is directly integrated with HELCOM initiatives through the Expert Group on Phytoplankton to harmonize image labeling across the Baltic Sea. It supports the assessment of phytoplankton species composition, abundance, and biomass indicators used to evaluate the ecological status of the region. Additionally, the standardized identification methods facilitate the detection of non-indigenous species and the monitoring of trends in their arrival and quantities.

Water Framework Directive

The product can provide essential technical support for evaluating the composition, abundance, and biomass of phytoplankton in coastal and transitional waters. By ensuring that imaging technologies deliver data comparable to traditional microscopy, it helps Member States maintain the consistency of biological quality elements used for ecological status classification. The harmonized labeling protocols ensure that high-frequency data from new sensors can be used reliably in official reporting cycles.

Example of agreement among experts for each morphotype obtained during the development of this Information Product. For more details, please see Siano et al. (2025).

To know more about this Information Product, read the report by Siano et al. (2025) OBAMA-NEXT Deliverable 2.2 Pelagic data processing from technology.

COPEPOD MEAN SIZE AND TOTAL ABUNDANCE ECOLOGICAL INDICATOR

Summary

This Information Product is a two-dimensional ecological tool that characterizes the relationship between the average size of copepods and their total population density. By utilizing high-resolution imaging and machine learning, this product provides a visual framework to track shifts in zooplankton community structure and ecosystem health.

Description of the Information Product

Zooplankton, specifically copepods, occupy a critical position in marine food webs, acting as a bridge between primary producers and higher trophic levels such as fish. Changes in their size structure can significantly alter the overall food web functionality and the quality of food available for planktivorous fish. The information product addresses the need for holistic management by providing a prerequisite understanding of zooplankton responses to environmental variability.

It is a modified version of the HELCOM Mean Size and Total Stock (MSTS) indicator and uses *in situ* size measurements captured by the Plankton Imager (Pi-10) to generate property-property plots, allowing researchers to project additional environmental variables and identify patterns associated with ecological state changes.

Location of the Learning Site where the product was tested.

How it works

- Capture *in situ* images using the Plankton Imager
- Apply machine learning for automated taxonomic identification
- Measure copepod body size and abundance automatically
- Create two-dimensional property-property plots of data
- Visualize mean size versus total population density
- Project biological, environmental, or other variables to reveal hidden patterns
- Identify shifts in community structure and functionality

Image of a copepod.

Relevance for EU Biodiversity Policies

Helsinki Convention

As this product is based on the HELCOM indicator MSTS, it can contribute with data on zooplankton species composition, abundance, and biomass. It provides a standardized method for assessing the state of pelagic biological communities. Additionally, if modified, the product has the potential to support the monitoring of non-indigenous species by tracking trends in the arrival, biomass, and abundance of new zooplankton types.

OSPAR

The product allows for monitoring changes in zooplankton community composition, biomass, and abundance. It supports biodiversity indicators related to plankton lifeform abundances and population demographics. Furthermore, if modified, the product can contribute to assessments of marine food web trophic structures, including the production of phytoplankton and the ecological network analysis indices required for regional environmental strategies.

Example of the results produced by this Information Product.

BENTHIC VEGETATION AND HABITATS

SPECIES DISTRIBUTION MODELS FOR THREATENED HABITATS AND SPECIES

Summary

This Information Product delivers high-resolution spatial predictions of threatened marine habitats and species using machine learning and statistical modelling. By integrating high-quality *in situ* observations with environmental predictors, the resulting models can be used to support the placement of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs), guides restoration planning, and facilitates ecosystem accounting. It provides a robust framework for quantifying habitat extent and assessing biodiversity distribution across coastal ecosystems.

Description of the Information Product

The Information Product provides high-resolution spatial maps that predict the occurrence and extent of threatened marine habitats and species. Within the OBAMA-NEXT project, the modelling logic used in this product has been refined to address critical data gaps in coastal management, focusing specifically on habitat distribution. These models utilize a combination of field data, collected through diver surveys and drop-video observations, and advanced machine learning algorithms to bridge the gap between local observations and regional management needs. The resulting spatial products are essential for identifying conservation priorities, as demonstrated in pilot studies for marine ecosystem accounting and study investigating valuable ecosystem service areas. By providing a standardized method for assessing habitat extent, this product serves as a foundation for evidence-based decision-making in marine spatial planning and nature-based climate solutions.

Location of the Learning Site where the Information Product was developed.

How it works

- Collect *in situ* data via divers and drop-video;
- Gather high-resolution environmental and bathymetric predictors;
- Apply machine learning and statistical modeling algorithms;
- Predict spatial occurrence of specific marine habitats;
- Generate high-resolution habitat distribution maps;
- Quantify habitat extent for regional ecosystem accounting;
- Identify high-value areas for conservation and restoration.

Relevance for EU Biodiversity Policies

Barcelona Convention

The product can support monitoring by Contracting Parties for the Mediterranean Action Plan by contributing to Ecological Objective 1 (EO1) and 2 (EO2) regarding species distributional range of habitats and species listed under appendix 1, and non-indigenous species.

Habitats Directive

The product can be a vital tool to support Member States' obligations under the Habitats Directive. It can be used to support the more effective designation of conservation areas under the Natura 2000 network (under Article 4). By providing spatial data on the distribution and range of species listed in Annex II, IV and V the product also enables better evaluation by Member States of the impact of their conservation measures, as required under Article 17 of the Habitats Directive.

Bucharest Convention

The product can contribute to biodiversity monitoring by providing data on the distribution of threatened macrophytobenthos and macrozoobenthos species. It can address the need for accurate spatial information to assess the status of regional biodiversity.

HELCOM

Under the Baltic Sea Action Plan, the product can inform the assessment of the MPA network and regional biodiversity. By providing detailed maps of habitat extent, the product can provide information in support of HELCOM's efforts in ecosystem accounting and the identification of gaps in the protection of key Baltic ecosystems.

Marine Strategy Framework Directive

The product contributes to partly meets several data needs under D1, D5, D6, D7 and D8. In particular, regarding distribution of benthic habitat, benthic habitat extent, benthic species distribution for sp under annex ii, iv, and v. When incorporated with scenario modelling, the product can be used to assess extent of adversely affected habitat.

Nature Restoration Regulation

If modified, the product can provide baseline spatial data needed for national restoration plans, specifically data relating to species and habitat distribution. By assessing current habitat extents and identifying areas suitable for recovery, the IP enables authorities to plan large-scale restoration efforts.

OSPAR

If appropriately modified, for the North-East Atlantic, the product could provide the spatial distribution of OSPAR-listed benthic habitats, the condition of benthic habitat communities and extent of benthic habitats in relation to physical disturbances. The product could also be modified to provide the distribution of listed OSPAR monitored species such as cetaceans, and pinnipeds. By incorporating eutrophication, the product could also be modified to assess the direct and indirect effects of eutrophication on species and habitat.

To know more about how to apply this Information Product, read the publications:

[Forsblom et al \(2025\) *Aquatic Conservation. Integrating Regulating Ecosystem Services in Marine Conservation Planning*](#)

[Virtanen et al \(2024\) *One Ecosystem. Marine Ecosystem Extent and Condition Pilot Accounts for Finland*](#)

UNDERWATER SPECIES RICHNESS MAP

Summary

This Information Product provides high-resolution maps of underwater species richness by aggregating data from 119 individual species distribution models. It identifies biodiversity hotspots—including macroalgae, vascular plants, and mosses—offering a critical tool for marine spatial planning, and the identification of high-value conservation areas.

Description of the Information Product

The Underwater Species Richness Map is a spatial product that depicts the diversity of underwater vegetation across marine areas, specifically the Finnish coast. By stacking and classifying predictions from published species distribution models (SDMs), the product transforms individual species data into a comprehensive biodiversity layer. This product encompasses 119 different species and serves as a vital resource for environmental managers to identify sea areas with exceptional richness and to account for the ecological value of benthic ecosystems in national and regional assessments. While currently focused on vegetation, the methodology is scalable and can be adapted to other taxa and regions to identify areas of high conservation priority.

Location of the Learning Site where the Information Product was developed.

How it works

- The different models are summed into one combined layer;
- The summed layer is classified into biodiversity classes;
- Output maps show classes from low to high biodiversity;
- Spatial resolution depends on the quality of environmental variables;
- Maps highlight specific hotspots with high underwater species richness.

Coastline in the Baltic Sea.

Relevance for EU Biodiversity Policies

HELCOM

The product can provide species richness data to measure condition of communities.

Marine Strategy Framework Directive

The product can provide species richness data for Descriptor 1 (biodiversity) and 4 (marine food webs).

Map depicting the biodiversity classes across the Finnish marine area, where high values indicate higher richness.

To know more about this Information Product, read the preprint:

[Wang et al \(preprint\) Children's exposure to biodiversity in residential environments across Finland.](#)

And to know more about the models used for the biodiversity layer read the publications:

[Forsblom et al \(2025\) Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems. Integrating Regulating Ecosystem Services in Marine Conservation Planning.](#)

[Virtanen et al \(2024\) People and Nature. Recreational land use contributes to the loss of marine biodiversity.](#)

MAPPING OF BIOMASS AND CARBON CONTENT OF COASTAL VEGETATION USING GREEN LIDAR ON DRONES

Summary

This Information Product utilizes drone-borne green LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) technology to create high-resolution 3-dimensional models of submerged coastal vegetation. By transitioning from traditional 2D mapping to 3D structural analysis, this product enables precise estimation of vegetation distribution and canopy height of for instance seagrass meadows, from which biomass and carbon stocks can be estimated. This approach provides a “step forward” in monitoring “blue carbon” habitats.

Description of the Information Product

Coastal “blue forests,” such as seagrass meadows and macroalgae, are vital for biodiversity and carbon sequestration, yet their structural complexity is often poorly captured by satellite or acoustic surveys. To address this, the product uses drones equipped with topobathymetric (green) LiDAR sensors capable of penetrating shallow waters to map the seabed and vegetation in 3D. The product can generate high-resolution bathymetry and topography, 3D habitat models providing canopy height and structural complexity, biomass and carbon stock estimates derived from canopy volume, and automated classification for habitat identification.

Tested in Learning Sites in Norway and the Balearic Islands, this product offers a cost-effective and reproducible solution for monitoring changes in coastal vegetation, assessing biomass and carbon inventories, and will in turn enable assessments of health of benthic habitats under anthropogenic pressure.

Location of the Norwegian and Balearic Islands Learning Sites.

How it works

-
 Deploys drone-borne green topobathymetric LiDAR sensors.
-
 Generates highly accurate 3D point clouds.
-
 Captures data at centi/decimeter-scale spatial resolution.
-
 Differentiates vegetation from seabed using LiDAR intensity.
-
 Calculates canopy height from 3D models.
-
 Estimates carbon stocks via volume-biomass relationships.

Example of high-resolution 3D model obtained in the Norwegian Learning Site.

Relevance for EU Biodiversity Policies

Barcelona Convention

The product contributes to the monitoring of coastlines, specifically supporting Ecological Objective 10 (Marine Litter). By providing high-resolution maps of coastal areas, it enables the assessment of the amount of litter washed ashore and deposited on coastlines.

Bucharest Convention

The product can provide data on the abundance, biomass, and seasonal variability of macroalgae and seagrass meadows. It can provide high-resolution monitoring of threatened macrozoobenthos species and their associated habitats. Its ability to generate reproducible 3D models facilitates long-term tracking of community composition and biomass shifts in coastal ecosystems.

Habitats Directive

The product supports Article 17 reporting by providing precise data on the distribution, range, and condition of Annex I benthic habitats. The high-definition mapping of seagrass and macroalgae allows Member States to quantify the proportion of habitat area affected by pressures and evaluate the effectiveness of conservation measures within Natura 2000 sites.

Helsinki Convention

The product informs biodiversity indicators by providing high-resolution data on the distribution and biomass of coastal vegetated habitats, and habitat niche volume related to its capacity to sustain biodiversity. It addresses data needs for assessing the status of benthic communities, non-indigenous species, and the impacts of eutrophication. The standardized drone-based workflow improves cross-border comparability of habitat assessments.

Marine Strategy Framework Directive

This product provides critical data for Descriptor 1 (Biodiversity), Descriptor 2 (Non-indigenous species), Descriptor 5 (Eutrophication), and Descriptor 6 (Seafloor Integrity). It delivers refined spatial data on the condition and extent of benthic broad habitat types, helping to determine Good Environmental Status. It can also provide data on physical characteristics on shallow seabeds and biomass of shallow benthic habitats.

Nature Restoration Regulation

The product is essential for tracking the success of restoration measures for coastal (Article 4) and marine (Article 5) habitats. It facilitates the monitoring requirements of Article 15(3) by providing evidence of improvements in habitat condition and the recovery of carbon sequestration capacity. The precision of LiDAR allows for the detection of small-scale changes in habitat quality that are often missed by traditional and more coarse monitoring tools.

OSPAR

The product contributes to biodiversity and eutrophication descriptors by mapping the distribution and condition of listed benthic habitats. It supports indicators related to seafloor disturbance and the condition of benthic habitat communities in relation to eutrophication effects.

Water Framework Directive

The product can strengthen ecological status assessments in transitional and coastal waters by providing detailed data on "other aquatic flora". It addresses the directive needs for monitoring the substrate and structure of the coastal bed and intertidal zones.

QUANTIFICATION OF HABITAT CARBON SEQUESTRATION

Summary

This Information Product integrates and combines high-resolution drone mapping with advanced eDNA and chemical sediment analysis to quantify the carbon sequestration potential of coastal habitats. By fusing remote sensing data with *in situ* tools, it identifies specific species contributing to “blue carbon” stocks and sequestration potential and maps their distribution at local and regional scales.

Description of the Information Product

The product represents a cutting-edge, multi-platform approach for monitoring and quantifying the climate mitigation potential of coastal “blue forests,” such as seagrass meadows and kelp forests. It overcomes traditional mapping limitations by combining state-of-the-art drone remote sensing with molecular (eDNA) and chemical (Total Organic Carbon and ^{210}Pb -based age estimation) analyses. This integration allows for the precise identification of carbon sources within marine sediments, distinguishing between local sequestration and transported organic matter. By applying machine learning to high-resolution imagery and using species-specific qPCR markers, it delivers a comprehensive assessment of both habitat extent, carbon stock density and sequestration potential.

Tested in Norway and in the Balearic Islands, this multi-method approach provides critical evidence base for including coastal ecosystems in national carbon inventories and informs nature-based solutions for climate change.

Location of the Learning Sites where the Information Product was tested.

How it works

- Fly drones with RGB and multispectral sensors;
- Annotate images for machine learning training;
- Classify coastal habitats using automated algorithms;
- Collect sediment cores from identified habitats;
- Extract eDNA from the sediment samples;
- Use qPCR to detect species-specific carbon sources;
- Analyse total organic carbon and ^{210}Pb in the laboratory;
- Integrate mapping data with carbon density values;
- Calculate total sequestration potential for regional scales.

Relevance for EU Biodiversity Policies

Marine Strategy Framework Directive

The product significantly enhances the availability of data needed by Member States for monitoring and reporting required under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive, concerning Descriptor 5 (Eutrophication). By providing quantitative data on organic carbon sequestration and burial rates, the product addresses recognized data gaps in assessing the pressure and state of benthic ecosystems. The use of species-specific eDNA markers allows for a detailed understanding of community composition and habitat condition, which are vital for determining Good Environmental Status.

Additionally, the high-resolution mapping of seagrass and macroalgae supports indicators related to habitat extent and seafloor integrity (Descriptor 6). The integration of organic carbon measurements directly complements physico-chemical monitoring, offering a more complete picture of carbon cycling and ecosystem carbon inventory and sequestration potential in coastal and offshore waters.

Example of coastal habitat classification based on drone imagery and ground truth data collection, image annotation, and machine learning classification.

To know more about this Information Product, read the following publications:

[d'Auriac et al \(2021\) NIVA report. Blue Carbon eDNA – A novel eDNA method to trace macroalgae carbon in marine sediments.](#)

[Frigstad et al \(2021\) Nordic Council of Ministers. Blue Carbon – climate adaptation, CO2 uptake and sequestration of carbon in Nordic blue forests.](#)

[Kvile et al \(2024\) MethodsX. Drone and ground-truth data collection.](#)

[D'Auriac et al \(submitted\) Frontiers in Marine Sciences. Tracing Species Specific Kelp eDNA in Marine Sediments for Blue Carbon Assessment Along the Norwegian Coast.](#)

[Lavin et al \(in preparation\). Blue carbon stocks and sequestration potential in seagrass meadows estimated using drone-borne sensors and AI/ML.](#)

DETECTING AND QUANTIFYING MICROPLASTIC ON BEACHES USING DRONES AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Summary

This Information Product utilizes high-resolution drone imagery and Artificial Intelligence (AI) to automate the detection, quantification, and a visual classification of macroplastics in coastal regions. By providing systematic and repeatable surveys, the product provides a solution to overcome limitations of traditional and manual beach litter monitoring, which is often labour-intensive and spatially restricted. This approach represents a “step forward” in marine litter quantification and management and offers a cost-effective tool to guide and document the efficiency of clean-up actions and litter monitoring in coastal environments.

Description of the Information Product

Marine litter, particularly macroplastics, poses a significant threat to coastal biodiversity and ecosystem health. Traditionally, monitoring relies on manual – human-on-the-ground counting which are difficult to scale across remote or rugged coastlines. This product overcomes these challenges by deploying drones equipped with RGB and near-infrared (NIR) sensors to map littered beaches. The primary outputs include high-resolution litter maps identifying visible objects down to 2–4 cm, ML-based counting and classification of litter types, and assessment of temporal dynamic analysis to track residence time and re-appearance rates.

Tested in Norway, this product provides a scalable solution for guiding beach clean-up events and supplying authorities with the evidence-based data needed for national and international reporting.

Location of the Norwegian Learning Site.

How it works

-
 Deploys drones systematically over coastal zones at high altitudes (>100meters).
-
 Captures high-resolution images using RGB and multispectral (MSI) sensors at spatial scales of a few centimetres.
-
 Identifies and counts objects using ML-based algorithms at size down to a few centimetres.
-
 Classifies plastics from other types of litter, with potential expansion to include characteristics such as colour, material, shape, and size.
-
 Monitor and document re-accumulation and clean-up actions through repeated temporal surveys.

Example of classification of marine litter using the AI models based on a drone image.

Relevance for EU Biodiversity Policies

Barcelona Convention

The product supports the Regional Plan on Marine Litter Management in the EU. It contributes to Ecological Objective 10 by providing standardized data on trends in the amount of litter washed ashore or deposited on coastlines. By automating the quantification process, it allows for cost-efficient and frequent monitoring of “hotspots,” helping to identify priority areas for intervention and tracking the progress of reduction measures.

HELCOM

The product informs marine litter indicators by providing precise data on the quantity, composition, and types of macrolitter found on beaches and the water surface. As well as the quantity and type of macrolitter found in biota. It supports regional assessments of pressure on the marine environment and helps evaluate the effectiveness of the Baltic Sea Action Plan.

Marine Strategy Framework Directive

This product is a critical tool for Descriptor 10 (Marine Litter), specifically addressing criteria D10C1 (number of items per category on the coastline). It can also contribute to Descriptor 8 (Contaminants), in particular D8C4 (chronic and acute pollution). The high-resolution spatial data provides a robust baseline for determining Good Environmental Status and allows Member States to monitor the dynamics of plastic pollution.

OSPAR

The product contributes to monitoring of marine litter on beaches. By documenting the effects of clean-up actions and estimating the pressure of plastics on nature over time, it supports the OSPAR North-East Atlantic Environment Strategy. The system’s ability to map remote areas like skerries and islands addresses significant data gaps in regional assessments of coastal litter distribution.

Drone used during the field work in the Norwegian Learning Site.

To know more about this information product, read the publications:

[Torskiv et al. \(2000\) NIVA-report. Detection of macroplastic on beaches using drones and object-based image analysis.](#)

[Gallitelli et al. \(2024\) Science of the Total Environment. Expert survey reveals visual and drone-based census as most effective techniques.](#)

LARGE-SCALE MAPPING OF BLUE CARBON STOCKS

Summary

This Information Product utilizes machine learning and Earth Observation data to generate spatially explicit maps of organic carbon stocks across European seagrass and saltmarsh ecosystems. By identifying habitats at risk and quantifying potential release from habitat loss, it provides a robust scientific basis for prioritizing conservation and restoration efforts as part of nature-based climate mitigation strategies.

Description of the Information Product

The product addresses the critical need for a comprehensive assessment of “blue carbon” ecosystems, specifically tidal marshes and seagrasses, which play a vital role in climate regulation by storing significant amounts of carbon in their sediments. When these habitats are degraded or lost, they not only stop sequestering carbon but also release large quantities of stored back into the atmosphere, turning from carbon sinks into sources.

This product quantifies these dynamics at a European scale by integrating harmonized habitat distribution maps with advanced geospatial modeling. By training machine-learning algorithms on observational data and relevant environmental predictors, the product identifies priority areas for conservation and restoration. Furthermore, the product develops a risk index derived from anthropogenic and environmental pressures to assess habitat vulnerability, providing the evidence needed for Member States to include coastal ecosystems in their national carbon inventories and climate action plans.

How it works

- Harmonize EU-wide habitat maps for seagrass and saltmarshes;
- Train machine-learning models using environmental predictors;
- Map organic carbon stocks across European coastal ecosystems;
- Assess protection status of all mapped blue carbon habitats;
- Develop risk index from anthropogenic and environmental pressures;
- Identify habitats most vulnerable to degradation and loss;
- Estimate release from potential habitat deterioration;
- Calculate uncertainty using Monte Carlo simulations and error propagation.

Relevance for EU Biodiversity Policies

Barcelona Convention

The product provides data on the distributional range of benthic biogenic habitats listed in Appendix I. While it identifies where these blue carbon ecosystems are located across the Mediterranean, it focuses on mapping the distribution of carbon stocks rather than evaluating the biological condition or health status of the communities.

Habitats Directive

For seagrass and saltmarsh habitats listed under Annex I, the product provides spatial information on their range and area. This data is essential for Member States' reporting requirements under Article 17, particularly for evaluating the extent of habitats.

HELCOM

The product contributes to the Baltic Sea Action Plan by mapping the distribution of key species such as angiosperms (e.g., *Zostera marina*). By providing a regional overview of carbon-rich habitats in the Baltic Sea, it supports efforts to understand the distribution of critical ecosystem types.

Marine Strategy Framework Directive

The product directly addresses data needs for Descriptor 1 (Biodiversity) regarding species and habitat distribution (Criteria D1C4 and D1C5). It provides high-resolution maps of habitat extent for coastal biogenic systems, which are necessary for assessing the suitability and range of species.

Nature Restoration Regulation

The product provides critical spatial information for tracking the extent of blue carbon habitats, which support the implementation and monitoring requirements of the Nature Restoration Regulation. The product's capacity to identify vulnerable habitats and quantify carbon stocks could significantly enhance the ability of Member States to evaluate restoration progress and assess the effectiveness of compensatory measures. By modelling potential emissions associated with habitat loss, the product might fill knowledge gaps regarding the climate mitigation impact of restoring specific biogenic habitats. This spatially explicit data could provide the evidence base needed for national restoration plans, helping to prioritize intervention areas where restoration yields the highest combined benefits for biodiversity recovery and carbon sequestration.

OSPAR

The product provides distribution maps for protected benthic habitats. It allows for a better understanding of the spatial footprint of carbon-sequestering ecosystems in the OSPAR region.

OC stocks (Top 30 cm)

Note: Color shows area-weighted OC stocks.

Example of map with assessment of organic carbon stocks in seagrass (A) and saltmarsh (B) habitats using this Information Product.

SPECIES DISTRIBUTION MODEL FOR EELGRASS

Summary

This Information Product delivers high-resolution predictions of eelgrass (*Zostera marina*) occurrence and depth limits by combining machine learning and long-term monitoring data. The model integrates key environmental drivers- light availability at depth, wave exposure (Maximum Exposure Index), and temperature—to produce spatially explicit distribution maps with quantified uncertainty estimates. Developed and validated for Danish coastal waters, the model supports habitat protection restoration site selection and marine spatial planning under EU directives. The product provides a practical framework for translating local eelgrass observations into management-ready spatial information across Danish coastal waters.

Description of the Information Product

The Information Product delivers a species distribution model for eelgrass (*Zostera marina*) using long-term national monitoring data and environmental predictors to map current distribution and ecologically meaningful depth limits. Developed for Danish coastal waters, the model draws on a large observation dataset covering more than a decade of monitoring, allowing eelgrass occurrence to be predicted at fine spatial scale across broad coastal areas.

The modelling framework goes beyond conventional probability-of-occurrence mapping by also estimating ecologically meaningful depth distribution limits, which are directly relevant for management. The outputs include presence-absence raster for eelgrass and a confidence map showing where predictions are most reliable. Together, these products provide a robust baseline for habitat conservation, restoration site prioritization and adaptive management.

Location of the Learning Site where the product was tested.

How it works

- Eelgrass monitoring data from national monitoring program are compiled across years;
- Environmental predictors are assembled at 50X50 m resolution;
- Random Forest model is trained and validated;
- Presence-absence and confidence maps are generated;
- Depth limits are estimated and validated against independent field surveys across multiple water bodies.

Relevance for EU Biodiversity Policies

Habitats Directive

The product contributes directly to biodiversity data needs for species and habitat distribution mapping under Annex I marine habitats, where eelgrass forms a key habitat-structuring component. The model produces spatially explicit maps of eelgrass occurrence, range, and depth-related habitat extent, enabling assessment of benthic biogenic habitat distribution, area and condition. By integrating environmental drivers and uncertainty quantification, the product can detect distributional shifts and support evidence-based assessments of habitat condition changes under anthropogenic pressure, directly informing conservation status reporting and site management.

Marine Strategy Framework Directive

The product contributes to multiple descriptors identified in the policy crosswalk. For Descriptor 1 (Biodiversity), it provides fine-scale species distribution data and habitat suitability maps for a foundation species. For Descriptor 7 (Hydrological Conditions), the model links habitat distribution to key environmental drivers such as light availability, exposure and temperature, supporting impact assessments of altered hydrological conditions on benthic habitats. The integration of validated ecological thresholds (light requirements, depth limits) with spatially explicit uncertainty estimates enables both state and pressure-impact evaluation, supporting Good Environmental Status (GES) determinations for coastal benthic ecosystems.

Nature Restoration Regulation

The product provides a modeling framework to evaluate both reference conditions and eelgrass restoration potential under different water quality scenarios. By running the model with improved environmental conditions (e.g., enhanced light availability following nutrient reduction), managers can identify areas where eelgrass could potentially re-establish if key limiting factors are addressed. This scenario-based approach enables spatial assessment of restoration opportunities across different coastal areas and quantifies the potential distribution gains achievable through catchment-scale management actions. The model thereby supports both restoration site prioritization and the design of water quality improvement measures needed to enable habitat recovery.

Water Framework Directive

The depth limit of eelgrass (Z_{max}) predictions aligns directly with the biological quality element for coastal waters, where eelgrass depth distribution serves as an indicator of ecological status. The model enables consistent, spatially comprehensive assessment of this indicator across water bodies, supporting monitoring, classification, and reporting requirements.

Example of the application of this Information Product to predict eelgrass distribution in the Danish Learning Site.

SEAGRASS MAPPING – DISTRIBUTIONS AND ECOLOGICAL STATUS

Summary

This Information Product utilizes drone-based remote sensing and machine learning to deliver high-resolution maps of seagrass distribution and condition. By integrating *in situ* ground-truthing with automated classification, it provides spatially comprehensive and comparable habitat data, tested across European coastal waters. This standardized approach overcomes long-standing inconsistencies in regional monitoring to support integrated ecosystem assessments.

Description of the Information Product

This product provides a coherent framework for monitoring seagrass (*Zostera spp*, *Posidonia oceanica*) and other vegetated coastal habitats using Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs). Historically, seagrass monitoring has been limited by fragmented, labor-intensive field methods and the surface-layer restrictions of satellite sensors. This product addresses these challenges by combining high-resolution drone imagery with sophisticated machine learning algorithms to automate habitat classification.

The product delivers detailed spatial data on habitat extent, patchiness, and temporal change. By applying common classification standards and upscaling local observations to regional scales, it should enable Member States to integrate consistent seagrass data into existing reporting frameworks. Ultimately, this methodology reduces field costs while improving the repeatability and cross-border comparability of marine biodiversity monitoring.

Location of the Learning Sites where the Information Product was tested.

How it works

- Deploy drones with RGB or multispectral (MSI) sensors;
- Collect high-resolution imagery, preferably during low tide;
- Gather *in situ* ground-truth data using USVs, ROVs, drop-down cameras or direct observations on shallow water;
- Annotate imagery according to hierarchical habitat class schemas;
- Train machine learning algorithms for automated classification;
- Generate accurate orthomosaics and seagrass distribution maps.

Relevance for EU Biodiversity Policies

Habitats Directive

The product provides data on the distribution, range, and condition of biogenic habitats listed in Annex I. It enables consistent tracking of trends in habitat area, potentially supporting evaluations of Favorable Conservation Status for sensitive seagrass communities.

Marine Strategy Framework Directive

This product may strengthen data available for Member States reporting under multiple descriptors by providing harmonized spatial information on vegetated benthic habitats. It can support data needs for Descriptor 1 (Biodiversity) for DIC4 and through some degree of community composition assessments and Descriptor 5 (Eutrophication) via seagrass cover indicators. Additionally, it potentially contributes to Descriptor 8 (Contaminants) by evaluating habitat condition in areas at risk from pollutants.

Nature Restoration Regulation

The product can provide supporting baseline spatial information needed to track the condition and extent of habitats referred to in Articles 4 (terrestrial, coastal and freshwater ecosystems) and 5 (marine ecosystems). It provides data to support Member States in monitoring restoration progress, including changes in species-habitat distribution and the evaluation of areas undergoing active restoration or compensatory measures.

Regional Sea Conventions

This product may inform regional assessments under Regional Seas Conventions and Action Plans for indicators related to species distribution, community composition, and population demographics of vegetated benthic communities. It could thereby support alignment between EU directives and regional frameworks by providing spatially coherent tools applicable across different sea basins. Specifically, it addresses data needs for angiosperm depth limits in the Baltic Sea and biomass variability in the Black Sea.

Example of maps generated using this Information Product to identify seagrass meadows and other habitats.

To know more about how to apply this Information Product, read the publications:

[Kvile et al \(2024\) *MethodsX*. Drone and ground-truth data collection, image annotation and machine learning: A protocol for coastal habitat mapping and classification. *MethodsX*](#)

[Staehr et al \(2025\) OBAMA-NEXT. D3.2 Synthesis report on remote sensing for mapping benthic habitats and organisms.](#)

[Gundersen et al \(2025\) OBAMA-NEXT. D3.4 Synthesis report on best practices for benthic monitoring programmes.](#)

COASTAL VEGETATION MAPPING – UPSCALED FROM DRONES TO SATELLITES

Summary

This Information Product utilizes the fusion of high-resolution, small-scale drone data with lower-resolution, large-scale satellite imagery to upscale coastal vegetation maps. This approach enables the comprehensive mapping of macroalgae, seagrass, soft sediments, and other broad scale habitat types across large geographic areas.

Description of the Information Product

This product addresses the challenge of monitoring coastal ecosystems over large areas while maintaining high ecological detail. By integrating centimetre-scale drone imagery with coarser satellite datasets, such as Sentinel-2, it bridges the gap between local field observations and regional management needs. This data fusion method uses machine learning algorithms to learn from high-resolution drone-based habitat maps and predict distributions over much larger satellite swaths. The result is a cost-efficient, repeatable, and scalable monitoring solution that provides coherent habitat maps across diverse sea basins, reducing regional inconsistencies and supporting large-scale ecosystem assessments.

Location of the Learning Sites where the Information Product was tested.

How it works

- Collect high-resolution drone data and *in situ* reference data at selected sites;
- Build an ML algorithm based on drone images and annotations, and create a local drone-based habitat prediction map;
- Acquire large-scale satellite images or the region;
- Upscale local classifications using the drone-based habitat map as training data;
- Predict vegetation extent across entire satellite scenes;
- Monitor temporal changes in habitat distribution annually or seasonally.

Example of upscaled maps derived from predictions based on two drone surveys (orange polygons) along the western coast of Norway (credits: SeaBee)

Relevance for EU Biodiversity Policies

Bucharest Convention

The product supports monitoring under the Bucharest Convention by providing data on the abundance and seasonal variability of macroalgae and angiosperm species. By mapping the community composition of microphytobenthos at an overall level, it addresses regional data needs for tracking biodiversity trends and assessing the status of e.g. threatened or submerged aquatic plants.

Habitats Directive

The product supports Member States' reporting requirements under Article 17 by providing data, particularly on the distribution, range, and condition of biogenic habitats listed in Annex I. It enables consistent tracking of trends in habitat area, potentially supporting evaluations of Favorable Conservation Status for sensitive seagrass communities.

HELCOM

This product can inform evaluations for the Baltic Sea region by delivering precise information on macroalgae and angiosperm distribution and sometimes also their depth limits. It supports strengthened regional assessments of community composition, including macroalgae and angiosperm species composition and population abundance at an overall level, which are critical for identifying habitat loss and physical disturbance.

Marine Strategy Framework Directive

The product contributes to data needs for multiple descriptors by offering harmonized spatial information on benthic habitats. It supports Descriptor 1 (Biodiversity) through assessments of habitat distribution and condition, Descriptor 5 (Eutrophication) via macroalgal cover and abundance indicators, and Descriptor 8 (Contaminants).

Nature Restoration Regulation

The product provides essential baseline and monitoring data needed for national restoration plans, specifically under Article 15(3)(p) including for trends, condition and quality of relevant habitat types (in Articles 4 and 5).

OSPAR

The product facilitates the assessment of OSPAR-listed benthic habitats by documenting their distribution. It contributes data relating to indicators for seafloor integrity, specifically evaluating the extent of physical disturbance and the environmental status of sentinel seabed species across pressure gradients.

Water Framework Directive

The product delivers information that can be transformed to biological quality elements, specifically the composition and abundance of macroalgae, angiosperms, and macrophytes in coastal and transitional waters. Its upscaling capability improves the spatial resolution and repeatability of ecological status assessments in a cost-efficient manner, potentially helping Member States diagnose pressures and harmonise reporting.

To know more about how to apply this Information Product, read the publications:

Azhar et al (in preparation) A standardised multi-scale protocol for coastal benthic habitat mapping using UAV and satellite remote sensing

[Gundersen et al \(2024\) NIVA report. Method development for mapping kelp using drones and satellite images: Results from the KELPMAP-Vega project.](#)

[Gundersen et al \(2025\) OBAMA-NEXT. D3.4 Synthesis report on best practices for benthic monitoring programmes.](#)

MAPS OF REGULATING ECOSYSTEM SERVICES

Summary

This Information Product generates high-resolution spatial maps of seven regulating ecosystem services in the Finnish marine area, identifying key service supply zones by integrating species distribution models (SDMs) with species-specific traits. These maps highlight hotspots for services like carbon sequestration and nutrient filtration to guide effective marine conservation to also safeguard ecosystem functioning.

Description of the Information Product

This product provides high-resolution map layers depicting the supply of seven regulating ecosystem services provided by benthic habitats: bioremediation, filtration of harmful substances, nutrient filtration, erosion control, flood control/coastal protection, net oxygen production, and carbon sequestration. Unlike simple species-richness maps, this product incorporates detailed species-specific traits, such as biovolume, biomass, lifespan, and growth form, to provide a more realistic quantification of the services delivered by macroalgae, macrophytes, and fauna.

The final products are 20x20 m gridded maps that identify key ecosystem service areas, which are predominantly located in shallow coastal ecosystems and adjacent reef areas. By identifying where service supply is highest, this product enables environmental managers to account for ecological functions in conservation planning and supports the expansion of marine protected area networks. It specifically addresses the need to protect not just species, but the functional roles they play in maintaining healthy marine ecosystems.

Location of the Learning Site where the Information Product was developed.

How it works

- Uses spatial predictions from species distribution models;
- Species traits help quantify individual contributions to ecosystem services;
- Scientific literature connects specific species models to ecosystem services;
- Individual models are combined to identify high-value supply areas;
- High-resolution maps display the relative amount of service supply;
- Spatial prioritization of the resulting layers highlight hotspots in shallow coastal and reef ecosystems.

Image of the Baltic Sea coastline.

Relevance for EU Biodiversity Policies

Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework

The product supports progress towards Target 3 (conserve 30% of land, waters and seas) by providing data that enables areas of high ecosystem service value to be identified.

The product can facilitate area-based conservation efforts to safeguard critical ecosystem functions and services alongside species diversity.

Map depicting the the relative supply of carbon sequestration service provided by macrophytes and vasular plants in the Finnish Marine Area (Forsblom et al. 2025).

DATA- AND CRITERIA -BASED IDENTIFICATION OF HIGH-DEFINITION HABITAT TYPES

Summary

This Information Product represents a step forward in harmonized marine mapping by refining the spatial classification of critical coastal and marine habitats. By applying standardized geomorphometric algorithms to open-access datasets, this product addresses inconsistencies in national monitoring. It provides a repeatable framework for identifying high-definition habitat types, such as sandbanks, estuaries, and lagoons, ensuring that biodiversity assessments are based on transparent and comparable methodologies across European sea basins.

Description of the Information Product

Historically, habitat mapping across Europe has suffered from “border effects,” where different Member States use varying definitions and survey methods for the same habitat types. This Information Product overcomes these limitations by using a standardized, criteria-based approach to identify and delineate Annex I habitat types. Tested in the Kattegat, the product moves away from subjective interpretation toward a technology-driven classification that integrates bathymetric, sedimentological, and satellite data.

The primary output is a suite of high-definition spatial layers that accurately reflect the distribution and extent of habitats, including sandbanks, estuaries, intertidal mudflats and sandflats, coastal lagoons, and large shallow inlets and bays.

Location of the Learning Site where the Information Product was developed and tested.

How it works

- Integrates EMODnet bathymetry and sediment datasets;
- Applies standardized geomorphometric algorithms;
- Uses Copernicus Earth Observation variables;
- Classifies habitats;
- Cross-checks findings against satellite imagery;
- Validates polygons using biological sentinel species;
- Automates workflows for repeatable regional mapping.

Relevance for EU Biodiversity Policies

Barcelona Convention

If applied in the relevant region, the product could contribute to the monitoring of benthic and pelagic habitats listed in Appendix 1, specifically addressing Ecological Objective 1 (Biodiversity) and Ecological Objective 7 (Hydrological conditions). By refining the spatial classification of habitats, it provides data on the distributional range and condition of these ecosystems. If modified for the Mediterranean context, the product's geomorphometric and remote sensing workflows can help identify the location and extent of habitats directly impacted by hydrographic alterations.

Habitats Directive

The product allows refining of habitat maps for Annex I habitat types in support of Member States reporting requirements under Article 17. The use of high-resolution geospatial data allows for a more accurate assessment of habitat distribution, range, and condition compared to traditional national reporting. This enables Member States to compare existing Natura 2000 areas against data-driven habitat maps to support more effective designation and evaluation of conservation areas under article 17 by identifying protection gaps and evaluating the proportion of habitat area affected by pressures.

Nature Restoration Regulation

The product supports monitoring of trends in habitat quality for the purpose of restoration measures for coastal (Article 4) and marine (Article 5) habitats by providing high-definition maps that support effective tracking of habitat extent, location and condition. This supports monitoring within national restoration plans as required under Article 15(3). The product's ability to distinguish between different habitat types supports measures taken to meet restoration targets at the level of each biogeographical region.

OSPAR

If modified, the product can contribute with data needed for biodiversity descriptors by providing data on the distribution and condition of listed benthic habitats.

Example of map produced with this Information Product with the identification of different habitat types.

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF SPECIES DISTRIBUTION MODELLING AND REMOTE SENSING SPATIAL DISTRIBUTION OF COASTAL HABITATS TECHNIQUES IN PREDICTING

Summary

This Information Product provides a rigorous comparison between satellite remote sensing and species distribution modelling (SDM) for mapping benthic habitats. By evaluating conventional mapping methods across seven diverse sites, ranging from the Black Sea to the North Atlantic, the product offers evidence-based guidance on selecting the most effective techniques for monitoring habitat extent and supporting marine spatial planning.

Description of the Information Product

The product investigates the performance of two primary spatial mapping approaches across seven study sites: the Møre coast (Norway), the Bothnian Sea (Finland/Sweden), the Northeast Gulf of Riga (Estonia), the Danish Straits, the Wadden Sea (Netherlands), the Nessebar coast (Bulgaria), and the Saronikos Gulf (Greece). This wide geographical scope allows for the assessment of mapping techniques in the Northeast Atlantic, the Mediterranean Sea, the Black Sea, and the Baltic Sea.

The study utilizes high-resolution environmental data and Sentinel-2 satellite imagery to produce gridded maps depicting the probability of occurrence for key marine habitats and species. While SDMs are noted for being relatively easy to apply with good quality environmental covariates, remote sensing models also have the potential to leverage the frequent revisit times of missions like Sentinel-2 to capture temporal changes. The resulting high-resolution outputs are intended to serve as Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs) for habitat extent, facilitating more accurate biodiversity assessments across European sea basins.

Location of the Learning Sites where the Information Product was tested.

How it works

- Comparison of satellite remote sensing (RS) and species distribution models (SDM);
- SDMs use environmental data to model the species distribution, whereas RS models use information retrieved from satellite images to classify habitats;
- Very high-resolution images improve classification at specific sites but can be expensive;
- Output maps depict probability of habitat occurrence;
- Resolution of the maps depend on the input data; SDMs 10m-1km, RS with Sentinel-2 10x10m, and RS with very high-resolution images 2x2m.

Relevance for EU Biodiversity Policies

Barcelona Convention

If appropriately modified and applied, the product can support monitoring for a range of indicators under including EO1 and EO7.

Bucharest Convention

The product can provide data on relevant species distribution, specifically distribution of threatened macrophytobenthos and macrozoobenthos species as well as additional data on relevant population demographics.

HELCOM

The product provides species distribution data needed for indicators for named species.

Habitats Directive

The product directly supports monitoring for species distribution as well as providing data for monitoring changes in habitat distribution and population size (relating to seagrasses).

Marine Strategy Framework Directive

By providing information on species distribution at a given point in time, the product supports monitoring needed for descriptors including 1, (DIC4, DIC6) and 8 (DIC8, DIC4) as well as components of descriptors 5, 6 and 7.

Nature Restoration Regulation

If appropriately modified the product can provide baseline spatial data required to identify extent and state of marine habitats listed in Annex II, such as seagrass beds and macroalgal forests. By identifying the most accurate mapping techniques in different contexts, it assists Member States in identifying spatial extents needed the development and implementation of National restoration Plans under the Regulation.

Example map showing the predicted distribution based on the very high resolution images (RF, XGB, SVM) for macroalgal habitat in the Bothnian Bay region in Finland.

BENTHIC FAUNA

MEDITERRANEAN (BLUE) MUSSEL BIOMASS ESTIMATION WITH 3D PHOTOGRAMMETRY

Summary

This Information Product introduces a non-destructive, high-resolution method for estimating the biomass of the Mediterranean mussel using 3D digital photogrammetry. By converting underwater imagery into digital surface models, the tool allows for the rapid assessment of mussel bed volume and biomass without the need for destructive sampling.

Description of the Information Product

The Mediterranean mussel (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*) is a foundational habitat-forming species in several coastal regions of different European seas, including the Black Sea. However, these communities face significant pressure from human activities and invasive species, requiring frequent and accurate monitoring. Traditional biomass estimation relies on labor-intensive, destructive sampling that removes organisms from their environment. This product overcomes this by utilizing underwater photogrammetry to create precise 3D reconstructions of mussel beds.

Developed and tested along the Bulgarian coast, the product uses a standardized workflow where scuba divers capture overlapping photographs within a sampling frame. These images are processed to generate 3D Digital Surface Models, from which the volume of the mussel community is estimated. By applying validated regression models that link volume to wet weight, researchers can accurately estimate the *in situ* biomass. This rapid, repeatable methodology provides a vital tool for assessing Good Environmental Status and tracking the population dynamics of both native mussels and their predators.

Location of the Bulgarian coast Learning Site.

How it works

- Conduct underwater scuba surveys on infralittoral reefs;
- Capture overlapping photographs within a 3D sampling frame;
- Process images to create high-resolution 3D digital models;
- Calculate precise volume from the digital surface models;
- Apply regression models to estimate biomass from volume;
- Link biomass data to predator-prey trophic indicators;
- Monitor population growth rates non-destructively over time.

Relevance for EU Biodiversity Policies

Barcelona Convention

If modified for Mediterranean reef systems, the product can support the monitoring of habitat distributional range and condition for typical species (Ecological Objective 1). It provides a scalable method to assess the biomass of biogenic habitats in Appendix 1. Furthermore, the technology has the potential to track the abundance and temporal occurrence of non-indigenous species in coastal risk areas.

Habitats Directive

This product supports Annex I habitat assessments by mapping the distribution and condition of biogenic habitats like mussel reefs. It can also inform seafloor integrity for non-biogenic habitats through high-resolution data on their physical state. By establishing quantitative baselines, it can track temporal trends and evaluate how pressures or restoration impact habitat area and quality.

HELCOM

While developed in the Black Sea, this product could be modified to address HELCOM's data needs regarding the abundance and biomass of soft-bottom macrofauna and benthic species composition. The non-destructive photogrammetry approach offers a harmonized way to monitor the condition of benthic biogenic habitats across different regional seas, supporting standardized assessments of ecosystem health.

Marine Strategy Framework Directive

This product directly supports MSFD Descriptor 2 (Non-indigenous species), specifically indicator D2C3, which evaluates the biomass ratio of species in consecutive trophic levels (e.g., native mussel prey vs. invasive predator). It also contributes to Descriptor 1 (Biodiversity) and D3C2 and D3C3 by providing high-quality data on the structure and biomass of benthic communities in broad habitat types, which is especially relevant given that mussels are included under this directive. It can also support Descriptor 4 (Marine Food Webs), as well as and Descriptor 5 (Eutrophication) as mussels are used for monitoring impacts of eutrophication.

Nature Restoration Regulation

The product can provide the spatial data needed to monitor the condition of biogenic habitat types in coastal and marine areas. It facilitates the tracking of restoration progress by providing non-invasive measurements of habitat quality and species biomass. This helps Member States ensure that restoration measures lead to a significant improvement in habitat status for protected species.

Water Framework Directive

The product contributes provides data on the state of the benthic invertebrate fauna in coastal waters, in particular the Mediterranean blue mussel. As a non-destructive tool, it enhances the ability of Member States to conduct frequent assessments of the ecological status of water bodies. The precision of 3D modeling allows for better detection of shifts in community structure caused by environmental pressures.

Example of 3D photogrammetry image obtained using this Information Product in the tested Learning site.

JOINT SPECIES DISTRIBUTION MODELLING INCORPORATING CO-OCCURRENCE PATTERNS AND ENVIRONMENTAL DEPENDENCIES

Summary

This Information Product uses Hierarchical Modelling of Species Communities (HMSC) to perform community level species distribution modelling for hard bottom benthic communities. By jointly predicting multiple species, it produces high resolution community maps that account for species co-occurrence and environmental dependencies.

Description of the Information Product

The product represents a significant advancement in ecological modeling by moving beyond single-species assessments to a holistic community-level framework. Using the HMSC statistical approach, the product links the distributions of multiple species to environmental conditions while simultaneously accounting for biological interactions and co-occurrence patterns. This method is particularly effective for rare or sparsely sampled taxa, as it “borrows strength” across different species to improve predictive accuracy. Developed and tested in the Gulf of Finland, this product produces spatially explicit maps of hard-bottom species, offering quantified uncertainty to support more reliable management decisions.

Location of the Learning Site where the Information Product was tested.

How it works

- Uses hierarchical Bayesian framework for modeling
- Links community patterns to environmental predictors
- Accounts for species co-occurrence and interactions
- Predicts multiple species distributions simultaneously
- Generates community-level metrics and functional group maps
- Includes quantified uncertainty for all predictions

Benthic macroalgae species present in coastal habitats.

Relevance for EU Biodiversity Policies

Bucharest Convention

This product can provide detailed state information on benthic communities. It has the capacity to track the abundance, biomass, and seasonal variability of macroalgae and seagrass species. Furthermore, it can support the monitoring of threatened macrozoobenthos species and provide essential data on community composition and biomass for macrophytobenthos and macrozoobenthos.

Habitats Directive

The product can provide precise data on species distribution and range for taxa listed in Annex II, IV, and V. It also can support the assessment of species found within Annex I habitats. By mapping community-level responses, it can help identify suitable areas for restoration and track the condition of protected hard-bottom habitats.

HELCOM

This product provides critical information on the distribution of key benthic species, including blue mussels and various macroalgae. Its ability to model community metrics makes it a valuable tool for assessing the status of benthic habitats in the Gulf of Finland.

Marine Strategy Framework Directive

The product can support Descriptor 1 (Biodiversity) assessments by providing data on the structure and composition of pelagic-benthic communities. It can also assist in evaluating Descriptor 4 (Food webs) through its mapping of trophic guilds and species composition, and Descriptor 5 (Eutrophication) by tracking macroalgal abundance and macrophyte community depth distribution. Its multi-species approach can facilitate a comprehensive assessment of Good Environmental Status across multiple biological descriptors.

OSPAR

The product can provide the necessary biological state information to assess the health of hard-bottom communities in the North-East Atlantic. By predicting suitable areas for habitat-forming species, it aids in the regional identification and protection of vulnerable marine ecosystems.

Water Framework Directive

This approach can deliver spatially explicit data on the composition, abundance, and biomass of aquatic flora and benthic invertebrate fauna. It can help Member States evaluate the ecological status of coastal waters by providing consistent monitoring of macroalgae and phytobenthos communities. The quantified uncertainty in its maps ensures that the biological quality elements required for reporting are assessed with scientific rigor.

Example of mapping product obtained when using this Information Product in the Finnish Learning Site to assess the distribution of the macroalgae *Vertebrata fucoides*.

FISH

ENVIRONMENTAL DNA (eDNA) FROM FISH, TO ASSESS ESTUARINE ECOLOGICAL STATUS

Summary

It responds directly to recognised gaps in fish monitoring, particularly the limited spatial coverage, inconsistent survey methods across different regions and Member States and lack of long-term datasets (D6.1). By enabling standardised and repeatable sampling across regions and time periods, eDNA provides a powerful tool to track changes in estuarine fish communities and improve the consistency of ecological assessments. The resulting eDNA-based fish index represents a step forward towards harmonised, cost-efficient and scalable estuarine monitoring across Europe.

Description of the Information Product

The eDNA-based estuarine ecological assessment (also known as the gAFI tool) applies molecular approaches to characterise fish communities in transitional waters. Validated in the Learning Site of the Bay of Biscay, the method uses eDNA metabarcoding to detect presence-absence patterns of fish species across multiple estuarine sites, offering a comprehensive perspective on community structure and temporal trends. This addresses a key issue previously identified by OBAMA-NEXT researchers in Deliverable 6.1: estuaries are among the least consistently monitored ecosystems in Europe, with fish data often being patchy, difficult to compare across regions and collected using gear-dependent methods that vary widely between Member States.

Location of the Basque Learning Site.

How it works

- ▣ Field teams collect and filter water samples to capture DNA fragments shed by fish;
- ▣ Water samples are sequenced using fish-specific genetic markers;
- ▣ Results are matched against curated reference databases to produce reliable species inventories;
- ▣ The molecular data are integrated into an index specifically adapted to WFD requirements, enabling ecological status assessments directly comparable to conventional methods.

This approach is replicable, non-invasive, scalable, and reduces the environmental impact associated with traditional trawling-based surveys. It also supports cross-site comparability and long-term monitoring by generating standardised datasets that can be used to evaluate changes in fish communities and harmonise assessments among Member States.

Because fish are one of the ecosystem components with the highest policy relevance, the development of a molecular, standardised monitoring workflow directly supports multiple reporting needs. Although developed for fish in estuarine environments, the workflow provides a transferable model for applying molecular tools to other biodiversity assessments, supporting the broader transition towards ecosystem-based monitoring.

Relevance for EU Biodiversity Policies

Habitats Directive

The product can strengthen information on species distribution and changes in species range for fish species. This contributes to the evidence base for Article 17 reporting, particularly regarding trends in species distribution and the influence of pressures on populations and habitats.

Water Framework Directive

The product supports the assessment of estuarine ecological status of transitional waters, specifically by providing molecular data on fish community composition, a core Biological Quality Element for transitional waters (Annex V). It delivers biological information that reflects the state of fish assemblages' composition, harmonised monitoring and improved intercalibration of assessments across Member States. The ability to generate consistent long-term datasets contributes to more robust reporting under Article 15 and provides a valuable complement to conventional ecological metrics.

Marine Strategy Framework Directive

By providing data on species composition, the eDNA metabarcoding method used in this product can deliver data relevant to the quantitative descriptors for determining good environmental status (Annex I), including biodiversity, seafloor integrity, and marine food webs. This supports the fulfilment of Member States' obligations relating the determination of good environmental status (Article 9) by providing data on species composition, it contributes with relevant data for Descriptor 1 (Biodiversity), Descriptor 6 (Seafloor integrity), and Descriptor 4 (Marine food webs).

OSPAR Convention

The product contributes to the OSPAR Convention, particularly to biodiversity descriptors that require information on population demographics. eDNA provides biological data that help characterise the state of fish populations, including changes in species composition. It also supports OSPAR's indicators on marine food webs by addressing data needs related to trophic structure and functional groups, and by offering biological evidence that can underpin assessments of regional ecosystem functioning when combined with complementary datasets.

Example of Good Environmental Status assessments in Basque country estuaries using this information product.

ENVIRONMENTAL DNA (eDNA) BASED FISH ABUNDANCE ESTIMATES FOR FISHERIES ASSESSMENT

Summary

This Information Product develops eDNA-based abundance estimates that can be integrated with acoustic-trawl surveys to improve fish biomass estimates for stock assessment. Building on the strengths of fisheries acoustics, the product combines quantification of species-specific DNA in seawater with acoustic data. The product can strengthen spatial biomass mapping and support more robust assessments for commercially important stocks, including data-poor or depleted fisheries.

Description of the Information Product

The product integrates eDNA measurements with acoustic-trawl observations to estimate biomass for fisheries assessment. The innovation relies on single-species molecular quantification (qPCR and digital PCR) to estimate DNA copies per litre from water samples. These eDNA-derived signals are then combined with acoustic-trawl data using a Bayesian statistical framework to estimate the spatial distribution and abundance of target fish stocks. The core output is a spatial abundance or biomass estimate that can be used alongside conventional survey products.

Location of the Basque Learning Site.

How it works

- Water samples are collected;
- Species-specific DNA is quantified using qPCR or digital PCR;
- eDNA concentration is used as an abundance proxy;
- Molecular data are integrated with acoustic backscatter in a Bayesian model;
- The joint framework produces spatial biomass and abundance estimates.

The method was developed and tested in the Learning Site Bay of Biscay for small pelagic stock assessment, specifically for European anchovy.

Example of European anchovy distribution and abundance map in the Bay of Biscay. Upper panel shows fish estimates whereas the lower panel shows changes to the estimates compared to the acoustic version only. Source: Claver et al. (2026).

Relevance for EU Biodiversity Policies

Barcelona Convention

The product contributes by providing single-species abundance data to biodiversity and ecosystem-based monitoring needs in the Mediterranean region. The product provides improved estimates of fish biomass and spatial distribution. It supports more robust evaluation of ecological status and trophic structure, strengthening regional reporting on biodiversity condition and pressures affecting fish communities.

Bucharest Convention

The product contributes to biodiversity monitoring by improving data on fish biomass, in the Black Sea region. The methodology enhances the assessment of population demographics and supports state-based indicators related to marine biodiversity and ecosystem functioning.

Habitats Directive

The product can support biodiversity reporting by strengthening information on species distribution and changes in species range for marine fish species relevant to Annex II, IV and V, as well as species associated with Annex I habitats. By combining eDNA and acoustic data, the product can provide special ranges of fish presence, enabling improved mapping of species distribution and detection of temporal shifts in range. This supports both state-based assessments of species distribution and impact-oriented evaluations of changes in species range under pressure, contributing to the evidence base required for Article 17 reporting.

HELCOM

The combined molecular-acoustic methodology improves the accuracy of fish biomass estimates while simultaneously providing taxonomic resolution, supporting indicators linked to species composition, abundance, and trophic guild structure. By enabling repeatable and harmonised assessments across monitoring programmes, the product has the capacity to strengthen the scientific basis for evaluating ecosystem status and contributes to improved regional consistency.

Marine Strategy Framework Directive

The product contributes to Biodiversity descriptor requirements by supporting state information on population abundance (D1C2) and species distributional range (D1C4), for non-commercial species. It contributes also to the Commercially Exploited Fish and Shellfish descriptor by providing abundance and biomass-related information relevant to stock status (D3C2), and to Marine Food Webs by supporting data needs on trophic structure through improved abundance estimates of key fish components

Nature Restoration Regulation

The product can support monitoring of habitat quality, extent and distribution for coastal and marine species by providing spatially explicit information on fish presence. The integration of eDNA and acoustic data can enable detection of changes linked to habitat condition, supporting the assessment of trends in areas under restoration. It can also help identify areas of deterioration or recovery, contributing to the evaluation of restoration effectiveness and progress towards restoration targets across biogeographical regions.

OSPAR

The product contributes to biodiversity and marine food web descriptors by enhancing the capacity to assess fish population demographics. The integration of eDNA with acoustic biomass measurements addresses gaps in linking species-level identification with quantitative abundance data, a limitation frequently noted in regional monitoring frameworks. This combined approach supports improved assessment of fish community condition, while increasing spatial coverage and methodological coherence across the North-East Atlantic.

SPECIES DISTRIBUTION MODELLING WITH EXPERT ELICITATION AND BAYESIAN CALIBRATION

Summary

This Information Product presents a cost-efficient methodology to improve species distribution maps by integrating traditional in situ observations with expert knowledge. By utilizing Bayesian calibration, the product accounts for the inherent subjectivity and potential biases of expert-drawn maps, combining them with field data to produce more accurate and high-resolution abundance predictions. This hybrid approach is particularly valuable for monitoring data-poor species or remote areas where extensive scientific surveys are financially or logistically challenging.

Description of the Information Product

Species Distribution Models (SDMs) are fundamental tools for marine conservation and resource management, yet their accuracy is often limited by the high cost and sparse coverage of scientific field surveys. While local experts often possess deep knowledge of species occurrences, their input is traditionally viewed as subjective and difficult to integrate into quantitative frameworks. This product bridges this gap by providing a novel statistical workflow that treats expert knowledge as a valuable, albeit biased, data source that can be formally calibrated.

Developed and tested in the Gulf of Finland, the Information Product focused on mapping the distribution of fish larvae for pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*). The process involves an expert elicitation phase where specialists summarize their beliefs into spatial maps, which are then analyzed alongside field data using Bayesian models. This allows the system to “learn” the skill of each expert and adjust their input accordingly.

Location of the Learning Site where this Information Product was developed.

The result is a significant improvement in predictive performance compared to models using survey data alone, providing managers with a robust, evidence-based tool for spatial planning and biodiversity assessment.

How it works

- Identify target species and environmental predictors;
- Invite experts to draw spatial occurrence maps;
- Conduct localized scientific field surveys;
- Apply Bayesian calibration jointly to expert assessments and field data;
- Assess skill weights of different expert inputs;
- Generate high-resolution species abundance maps;
- Validate model performance using cross-validation metrics.

Relevance for EU Biodiversity Policies

Barcelona Convention

If modified for the Mediterranean context, the product can support Ecological Objectives 1 and 2 (Biodiversity) by mapping the distributional range and condition of typical species and biogenic habitats. The methodology is particularly well-suited for identifying critical monitoring sites in regions where survey data is limited, helping to fulfill the requirement for monitoring across varying pressure gradients.

Birds and Habitats Directive

This product has the capacity to improve the mapping of distribution and range size and trends for protected marine bird species. By integrating expert knowledge on nesting or foraging grounds with available sighting data, it can support reporting on population demographics and the assessment of impacts on habitat quality across relevant seasons. It can also provide high-quality spatial data on the distribution and range of species listed in Annexes II, IV, and V of the Habitats Directive.

HELCOM

Having been successfully demonstrated in the Baltic Sea, this product provides a harmonized method to integrate historical expert knowledge with modern monitoring programs, strengthening regional assessments of ecosystem health and supporting the management of coastal fish stocks in particular with reference to population demographics.

Marine Strategy Framework Directive

The product is relevant to MSFD Descriptor 1 (Biodiversity), specifically supporting monitoring for indicators D1C2 and D1C4 regarding species population demographics, geographic distribution and range. Its ability to produce refined density maps for mobile species helps quantify the extent of habitat loss or degradation. Furthermore, it might be able to contribute to assessments of pelagic-benthic community structure by filling spatial gaps in species occurrence data.

Nature Restoration Regulation

This product can provide the spatial evidence required to track the quality of marine habitats (Annex II) habitats for protected marine species (Annex III). It can facilitate the development of restoration plans by Member States by identifying areas where habitat quality has deteriorated. The predictive maps can help to ensure that restoration measures effectively support species recovery at the biogeographical level.

OSPAR

The product can provide a robust framework to assess population abundance and distribution for a wide range of taxa, including fish and marine mammals. If modified for OSPAR regions, it can contribute to biodiversity state indicators by improving the resolution of species range maps.

Map with prediction for larval distribution in the study area. For more details see Kaurila et al (2026).

HIGH-RESOLUTION PREDICTIVE MAPS OF PROCESSES UNDERLYING FISH REPRODUCTION

Summary

This Information Product provides a spatially explicit modeling framework designed to understand and predict how environmental factors influence the reproduction of marine species. By integrating diverse data sources, including fisheries surveys and local environmental conditions, the product generates high-resolution maps of reproduction processes. This allows for a more detailed assessment of how coastal habitats support species renewal and how they may be affected by environmental changes.

Description of the Information Product

The product addresses the need to understand population dynamics at the spatial scale where reproduction actually occurs. Traditional models often aggregate data over large areas, potentially masking local environmental impacts on recruitment. This product utilizes a hierarchical Bayesian approach to link mechanistic population growth models, such as Ricker and Beverton-Holt, with species distribution models.

Tested using Baltic whitefish (*Coregonus lavaretus*) data from the Finnish coast of the Gulf of Bothnia, the model disentangles the effects of local environmental conditions, such as temperature and habitat quality, on different life stages. The resulting predictive maps provide a powerful tool for identifying essential fish habitats and assessing the resilience of fish populations to anthropogenic pressures and climate change. By providing high-resolution insights into the drivers of reproductive success, the product supports more precise and evidence-based spatial planning and conservation strategies.

Location of the Learning Site where this Information Product was developed.

How it works

- Identify target species and study area;
- Collect fisheries survey, fish larvae, and environmental data;
- Apply hierarchical Bayesian statistical modeling to integrate all data sources and parameterize a mechanistic population growth model;
- Quantify environmental effects on reproductive processes;
- Generate high-resolution spatial predictive maps;
- Validate model using cross-validation techniques.

Predictive maps of suitability, spawner density, proliferation rate and expected larvae density along the studied area. For more information see Pia et al (2025).

Relevance for EU Biodiversity Policies

Barcelona Convention

The product contributes with information to address the goal of maintaining healthy fish stocks (Ecological Objective 3). Specifically, it contributes to monitoring spawning stock biomass and fishing mortality by providing spatially explicit data on reproductive success. If modified for Mediterranean species and habitats, it could identify critical spawning grounds and support the assessment of population demographics for species listed in the Convention's appendices.

Habitats Directive

The product can provide detailed information on the distribution and range of fish species listed in the Annexes of the Habitats Directive. The use of the product for mapping essential reproductive habitats can assist Member States in monitoring "favourable conservation status" and identifying areas where human activities may impact species recovery.

Birds and Habitats Directive

The product has the capacity to contribute by modeling the populations of fish species that serve as primary prey for protected marine birds. Understanding the reproductive success and spatial distribution of these forage fish is essential for assessing the quality of foraging habitats. They can provide detailed information on the distribution and range of fish species listed in the Annexes of the Habitats Directive. Its ability to map essential reproductive habitats assists Member States in monitoring "favourable conservation status" and identifying areas where human activities may impact species recovery.

Bucharest Convention

The product supports monitoring needed in relation to objectives on biodiversity and the sustainable use of marine living resources. The product can contribute by modeling the reproductive processes of key species, thus supporting objectives related to biodiversity and the sustainable use of marine living resources.

HELCOM

The product is directly aligned with monitoring needs for population demographics of coastal and demersal fish. It addresses key data needs for fish species composition and abundance by providing high-resolution maps of reproductive processes. This strengthens regional assessments of ecosystem health and supports the identification of critical habitats for the renewal of fish populations.

Marine Strategy Framework Directive

The product is relevant to data needs under MSFD DIC2, DIC4 relating to population demographics and species distribution. It can provide quantitative data for assessing spawning stock biomass and the age and size distribution of populations. It can also support indicators related to species distributional range and population demographics, enabling a comprehensive assessment of Good Environmental Status. If appropriately modified, the product could support data needs under D3 (for commercially exploited fish and shellfish), D7 (change in habitat distribution) and D8 (impacts on biota).

Nature Restoration Regulation

If modified, the product can provide spatial evidence needed to monitor the quality of habitats for protected marine species as part of the monitoring undertaken by Member States within the scope of Article 5 (restoration of marine ecosystems). It can assist in identifying areas where restoration measures can most effectively enhance fish reproduction and population resilience. By tracking changes in reproductive success, the product helps evaluate the effectiveness of restoration efforts and ensures that conservation targets are met.

BIRDS AND MARINE MAMMALS

HABITAT SUITABILITY OF HARBOUR PORPOISES

Summary

This Information Product develops spatially explicit habitat suitability maps for key marine mammal species to support evidence-based conservation and adaptive management. By combining long-term telemetry data with Copernicus Earth Observation and other environmental predictors, this product quantifies spatiotemporal changes in suitable habitat and assesses how well existing protected-area networks continue to cover priority habitats over time.

Description of the Information Product

The product produces maps of marine mammal habitat suitability and habitat use, focusing on how these patterns shift across seasons and over multi-year periods. The work is grounded in the need to understand whether existing conservation measures, particularly Marine Protected Areas designated to protect key species, remain fit for purpose under changing environmental conditions. The product quantifies seasonal habitat suitability across the North Sea–Baltic Sea transition zone and evaluates temporal change in the overlap between suitable habitat and an established network of MPAs designated for harbour porpoise protection.

The approach is designed to be transferable to other wide-ranging species, including seals, and to support broader marine spatial planning and conservation decision-making. The product was tested in Learning Site Kattegat, where it demonstrates how telemetry-based habitat modelling can generate comparable, policy-ready spatial products that can be updated as new tracking data and environmental information become available.

Location of the Learning Site where the Information Product was developed.

How it works

- Telemetry location data are compiled for tracked individuals across years and seasons;
- Environmental predictors are assembled;
- Habitat suitability is modelled;
- Seasonal maps of habitat suitability and change are produced;
- Suitable habitat is overlaid with MPA networks to assess coverage and effectiveness over time.

Relevance for EU Biodiversity Policies

Barcelona Convention

The product contributes to biodiversity state assessments by mapping habitat suitability and, if appropriately modified, species distribution, in relation to environmental variability.

Birds and Habitats Directive

The product provides spatially explicit information on species distribution, habitat suitability and temporal change. By mapping seasonal patterns and long-term shifts in suitable habitat and overlaying them with Natura 2000 listed habitats, the product supports assessment of habitat range, conservation status and the continued effectiveness of protected areas. This strengthens evidence available for Article 12 (Birds Directive) and Article 17 (Habitats Directive) reporting by Member States.

Marine Strategy Framework Directive

The product contributes to Descriptor 1 (Biodiversity) by delivering mapped information on habitat distribution and change for protected marine mammals. It supports regional coherence in biodiversity assessments and can complement evaluations under related descriptors by identifying biologically relevant areas exposed to environmental pressures.

Nature Restoration Regulation

The product supports monitoring of habitat condition and species-related restoration for national restoration plans by quantifying changes in suitable habitat over time.

OSPAR

The product can support biodiversity assessments if modified other marine mammal species to provide standardised spatial products on habitat use and distribution. These outputs can complement abundance-based indicators and strengthen ecosystem-based evaluations at regional scale.

Map of long-term habitat suitability of harbour porpoises obtained using this information product. Source: van Beest et al. (2025).

HABITAT SUITABILITY OF SEALS

Summary

This Information Product provides the first comprehensive analysis of the at-sea distribution and habitat suitability for harbour seals (*Phoca vitulina*) and grey seals (*Halichoerus grypus*) in the Baltic Sea region. By integrating two decades of satellite telemetry data with haulout counts through advanced statistical modeling, the product generates high-resolution density and suitability maps. The product enable managers to identify critical habitats, assess interspecific competition, and evaluate the impacts of increasing anthropogenic pressures on these important apex predators.

Description of the Information Product

Understanding the at-sea distribution of marine mammals is essential for effective ecosystem management, yet traditional monitoring often focuses solely on haulout sites during moulting or pupping seasons. The product overcomes this limitation by utilizing Species Distribution Models (SDMs) to map the environmental conditions that seals rely on throughout their annual cycle. The product utilizes Generalized Additive Mixed Models (GAMMs) to link seal presence data with static and dynamic environmental variables such as bathymetry, sea surface temperature, and oxygen saturation.

The resulting maps reveal critical differences in species preferences, with harbour seals favoring coastal habitats more strongly than grey seals, and identify areas where suitable habitat remains unoccupied due to historical hunting and pollution. By identifying these “unfilled” habitats and areas of high species overlap, the product provides a predictive tool for regional sea conventions and national authorities to manage recolonization and mitigate conflicts with human activities like shipping, fisheries, and offshore construction.

Location of the Learning Site where the Information Product was developed.

How it works

- Compile multi-decade satellite telemetry from many seals;
- Integrate regional census data from seal observation sites;
- Select static environmental variables like depth and distance;
- Incorporate dynamic variables like temperature and oxygen levels;
- Apply Generalized Additive Mixed Models for spatial analysis;
- Calculate habitat suitability based on environmental preferences;
- Generate relative population density maps for entire regions;
- Validate models by comparing suitability with actual distribution.

Harbour seal (*Phoca vitulina*).

Relevance for EU Biodiversity Policies

Barcelona Convention

The product can provide data on the distributional range of marine mammals. It is particularly relevant for mapping the habitat range and condition of pelagic habitats for typical species listed in the convention.

Birds and Habitats Directive

Although focused on seals, the modeling methodology is applicable to other mobile marine predators, such as seabirds. The product can be modified to support reporting on distribution and range trends for species listed in the Directive's checklist. This supports the assessment of impacts on habitat quality and population trends across relevant seasons. The also supports the Habitats Directive, as grey seals are listed under Annexes II and V. It provides the necessary evidence base for designating Special Areas of Conservation by identifying important habitats.

HELCOM

Having been developed specifically for the Baltic Sea region, this product addresses critical data needs for pelagic and demersal species distribution and abundance. By providing harmonized at-sea density maps, it strengthens regional assessments of ecosystem health and supports the management of recolonizing species.

Marine Strategy Framework Directive

The product is relevant to monitoring Descriptor 1 (Biodiversity), specifically indicator DIC2 regarding the geographic spread and distribution of species. It provides quantitative data on the distributional range and pattern of marine mammals within the water column. This enables a more accurate assessment of the extent of habitat loss or degradation for apex predators.

Nature Restoration Regulation

The product provides spatial data required to ensure that the deterioration of habitats for protected species is not significant at the biogeographical level. It assists in tracking the quality of habitats for marine species referred to in the regulation. The maps can be used to set and monitor restoration targets for coastal and marine areas

OSPAR

The product can provide a robust methodology to assess population abundance and distribution for grey and harbour seals (indicators BB1 and M3). If modified for OSPAR regions, it can identify changes in species range and habitat quality. This supports the evaluation of whether anthropogenic pressures are compatible with the conservation of marine mammal populations.

Example of the map produced using this Information Product to identify habitat suitability of seals.

POPULATION ESTIMATES OF SEABIRDS BASED ON DRONE IMAGES AND OBJECT RECOGNITION

Summary

This Information Product leverages high-resolution drone imagery and advanced Artificial Intelligence (AI) to provide accurate, repeatable, and non-intrusive population estimates of coastal seabirds. By replacing or augmenting labour-intensive manual counts with an automated machine learning pipeline, the product enables large-scale monitoring of colonies with minimal human disturbance. This approach is particularly effective for tracking population trends, breeding success, and species distribution across extensive coastal areas, providing a robust data foundation for European biodiversity management.

Description of the Information Product

The product consists of a comprehensive monitoring system designed to address the logistical challenges and inaccuracies associated with traditional seabird surveys. Developed and tested by the SeaBee drone infrastructure in Norway, the product focuses on surface-nesting species such as gulls, terns, and cormorants. It utilizes a state-of-the-art AI-based pipeline to process vast volumes of aerial imagery, transforming raw pictures into actionable population data.

A key innovation of this product is its ability to identify not only adult birds but also chicks in the colonies, which provides critical data on breeding success that was previously difficult or impossible to obtain without causing significant disturbance. The far-reaching drones and high spatial resolution allow for the detection of nests and individuals in remote or inaccessible locations. Furthermore, the system can be modified to also monitor seabirds outside the breeding season and near human infrastructure, such as offshore wind farms, where traditional survey methods are often constrained.

Location of the Learning Site where the Information Product was developed.

How it works

- Drones fly grid patterns over colonies from a distance;
- RGB and thermal sensors capture high-resolution imageries including nesting birds;
- AI models automatically identify and count individual birds;
- Expert validation ensures high accuracy and data quality;
- Drone images are uploaded to open-access geospatial platforms, and population estimates are incorporated into national monitoring programs.

Relevance for EU Biodiversity Policies

Barcelona Convention

The product contributes to achieving Ecological Objective 1 (EO1 – Biodiversity) by providing state data on the abundance and distributional range of seabird species listed in Appendix 1. It can also contribute to EO2 by providing data relating to the distribution of non-indigenous species.

Birds Directive

The product directly supports Member States' reporting requirements for population size, distribution and range of all species listed in the 'Complete checklist of species to be reported. It is particularly valuable for monitoring Annex I species and identifying trigger species for Special Protection Areas (SPAs).

Habitats Directive

The product supports Member States' reporting requirements under Article 17 by providing high-resolution data on the "state" of species, including population size, species distribution as well as data on impacts including trends in species range and trends in population size. The product can also be adapted to assess the quality of habitats for protected species in coastal zones.

HELCOM

The product provides data on species distribution and population abundance that is aligned with the Baltic Sea Action Plan with respect to regional biodiversity indicators and tracking trends in the abundance of key marine bird species.

Marine Strategy Framework Directive

This product supports Member States monitoring and reporting through assessments for Descriptor 1 (Biodiversity) and Descriptor 4 (Food webs) by providing primary data on criteria related to population abundance (DIC2) and species distribution (DIC1).

Nature Restoration Regulation

The product provides essential baseline and monitoring data needed for national restoration plans, specifically under Article 15(3)(p) to track the quality of habitats for marine species in areas subject to restoration measures.

OSPAR

The product addresses data needed for OSPAR assessments in relation to indicators such as Marine Bird Abundance (S5 BB4/BB23 B1) and Breeding Success (S5 BB5 B3). The ability to count chicks with high accuracy provides a step-change in tracking reproductive productivity trends.

Example of map produced using this Information Product in a seabird survey.

ESTIMATING SEA MAMMAL POPULATIONS USING DRONE IMAGERY AND AI-DRIVEN OBJECT RECOGNITION

Summary

This Information Product utilizes high-resolution drone imagery and advanced Artificial Intelligence (AI) to automate the monitoring of seal populations at coastal haul-out sites. By employing both visual (RGB) and infrared sensors, the system captures detailed aerial data that is then processed through a machine learning pipeline to identify and count species such as Harbour and Grey seals. This approach enables large-scale, cost-effective, and non-intrusive population assessments, providing critical data for marine management and conservation strategies.

Description of the Information Product

The product provides a scalable system for monitoring seal colonies by moving from small-scale local surveys to long-range, autonomous flight operations. It addresses the limitations of traditional monitoring, which often relies on labour-intensive manual counts from vessels or expensive manned aircraft. For local assessments, small drones can be launched from boats to test infrared technology, while long-range operations utilize Vertical Take-Off and Landing (VTOL) drones to cover extensive groups of skerries along pre-programmed transects.

The core of the product is the AI-based SeaBee pipeline that includes data acquisition, archiving, and automatic detection. Trained on datasets gathered over several years, the machine learning algorithms can distinguish seals from rocky backgrounds. This technology is potentially useful for assessing the impact of increased maritime activities, such as offshore wind and aquaculture, on coastal ecosystems.

Location of the Learning Site where the Information Product was developed.

How it works

- VTOL drones fly autonomous transects over known seal colonies.
- High-resolution RGB cameras capture detailed images of haul-out sites.
- Infrared sensors detect heat signatures to improve identification success.
- Machine learning algorithms automatically identify and count individual seals.
- Validated data is archived for potential use for wildlife management.

Relevance for EU Biodiversity Policies

Barcelona Convention

The product partly addresses data needs for the Integrated Monitoring and Assessment Programme in relation to Ecological Objective 1 (EO1) by providing data on the abundance and distributional range of marine mammals listed in Appendix 1. It can also be modified to assess the impacts of pollution events on these species.

Habitats Directive

This product directly fulfils Member States assessment and reporting requirements in relation to Annex II, IV, and V species. It provides precise data on population size, species range trends, and the proportion of populations affected by environmental pressures – if developed further.

HELCOM

The product contributes to assessing the population abundance and distribution of Harbour seals and Grey seals. It also supports assessments of nutritional and reproductive status.

Marine Strategy Framework Directive

This product supports Member States monitoring and reporting through the assessments for Descriptor 1 (Biodiversity) by providing data on criteria DIC2 (population abundance) and DIC4 (distributional range).

Nature Restoration Regulation

If modified, the product can monitor the quality of habitats for marine species in restoration areas as needed for by Member States under Article 15(3)(p). It helps track targets for species referred to in the regulation's coastal and marine articles.

OSPAR

The product provides essential state data on the population abundance of Atlantic Grey seals and Harbour seals (S5 BB1 M3). It also supports data needs for OSPAR assessments in relation to indicators for seal pup production (S5 BB3 M5) and general habitat quality.

Example of sea mammal counts using this Information Product.

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